

A GREEK ALCHEMICAL EPIGRAM
IN ITS MIDDLE BYZANTINE CONTEXT

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Abstract. This article examines the dedicatory epigram of the earliest and most important witness to the Greek alchemical corpus, the tenth-century manuscript donated by Cardinal Bessarion to the Republic of Venice, Biblioteca Nazionale Marciana MS gr. 299, as a window onto the cultural coordinates of the manuscript's middle Byzantine readers. Scrutiny of the epigram's meter, language, literary conventions, and the handwriting of the scribe who copied it into the manuscript point to a tenth-century date not only for the manuscript but also for the epigram itself and make it possible to situate the epigram, and with it the alchemical manuscript that contains it, within the mainstream of middle Byzantine elite culture.

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Alchemy has often been relegated to the fringes of the history of culture and science. Associated with ‘mysticism’ or fraud or both, the practices, discourses and theoretical frameworks grouped today under the banner of alchemy have had a tendency to leave historians of science unimpressed, especially for the medieval period. Historians of monotheistic religions, too, have tended to leave alchemy to one side, seeing it as incompatible with faith in the one true God, if not openly, then at least in secret. The anonymity and pseudonymity of alchemical texts, and our difficulty in interpreting their contents, serve as a further pretext for Byzantinists, Syriacists and Arabists to leave these historical curiosities to specialists who dedicate themselves to studying alchemy as a world apart from ambient cultures.

But who, in fact, were alchemists? That is, who were the men and women who wrote, read and used the texts labelled ‘alchemical’ by modern scholarship, or who carried out the procedures described in those texts? What were their social milieus, their cultural backgrounds? Or if we cannot for the most part know who they were, what can we glean about the hypothetical reader which alchemical texts construct? In order to begin to answer such questions for the middle Byzantine period, this article focuses on a single piece of evidence, the dedicatory epigram of the earliest known manuscript witness to the collection of texts known as the Greek alchemical corpus. By situating the epigram within the mainstream of elite

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Conventions and footnote abbreviations:

BAV = Vatican City, Biblioteca Apostolica Vaticana
BHG = *Bibliotheca Hagiographica Graeca*, ed. F. Halkin,
3 vols, Brussels 1957 (numbered entries)
BnF = Paris, Bibliothèque nationale de France
BSB = Berlin, Staatsbibliothek

CAAG = *Collection des anciens alchimistes grecs*, ed. and
tr. M. Berthelot and C.-É. Ruelle, 3 vols, Paris
1887–88

DBBE = Database of Byzantine Book Epigrams [only
available online]

‘diktyon’ numbers refer to the unique identifiers
assigned to Greek manuscripts by the Diktyon
network, which provides entries on these manu-
scripts in the Pinakes database [only available
online]

Laurenziana = Florence, Biblioteca Medicea Lauren-
ziana

LSJ = *A Greek-English Lexicon*, ed. H. G. Liddell and
R. Scott, rev. H. S. Jones, 9th edn with revised
supplement, Oxford 1996 [available online as LSJ -
The Online Liddell-Scott-Jones Greek-English Lexicon]

M = Venice, Biblioteca Nazionale Marciana MS gr.
299

NLR = St Petersburg, National Library of Russia

ODB = *The Oxford Dictionary of Byzantium*, ed. A.
Kazhdan et al., Oxford 2005

TLG = *Thesaurus Linguae Graecae* [only available
online]

middle Byzantine book culture, I aim to show that it presupposes precisely the same sort of reader as other high-brow Byzantine literature.

Historians of early modern science have been at the forefront of attempts to reintegrate social and cultural context into our study of alchemy.¹ Meanwhile, Islamicists have begun to reconsider earlier judgements about the place of alchemy in elite Muslim circles of the early Islamic period.² And though it has long been known that famous medieval scholars in the Islamic world were often interested in alchemy, only recently has this phenomenon been probed more closely.³ For the case of Greek alchemy, specialists have to a certain extent considered the ancient social and cultural contexts in which some Greek alchemical texts were produced;⁴ but similar work on the Byzantine contexts in which those texts were preserved, studied and reshaped, and new ones composed, has only just begun.⁵

This state of the field is particularly striking because our earliest extant manuscript witness to the Greek alchemical corpus is a middle Byzantine one: Venice, Biblioteca Nazionale Marciana MS gr. 299 [hereafter: M].⁶ When historians

1. E.g., B. J. T. Dobbs, *The Foundations of Newton's Alchemy*, Cambridge 1975; P. H. Smith, *The Business of Alchemy: Science and Culture in the Holy Roman Empire*, Princeton 1997; W. R. Newman and L. M. Principe, 'Alchemy vs. Chemistry: The Etymological Origins of a Historiographic Mistake', *Early Science and Medicine*, III, 1998, pp. 32–65; T. Nummedal, *Alchemy and Authority in the Holy Roman Empire*, Chicago 2008; W. Newman, *Newton the Alchemist*, Princeton 2019.

2. G. Saliba, 'A New Alchemical Poem Attributed to Khālid b. Yazīd (d. ca. 705)', *Ambix*, LXIV, 2017, pp. 220–33, esp. 226–31; *contra* M. Ullmann, 'Ḥālid ibn Yazīd und die Alchemie: Eine Legende', *Der Islam*, IV, 1978, pp. 181–218, who argued that the Umayyad prince Khālid ibn Yazīd did not write the alchemical works ascribed to him.

3. R. Forster, 'Arabic Alchemy: Texts and Contexts (Sección Monográfica: Introducción)', *Al-Qanṭara*, XXXVII, 2016, pp. 272–73.

4. See esp. O. Dufault, *Early Greek Alchemy, Patronage and Innovation in Late Antiquity*, Berkeley 2019 [available online]. See also the introductions and commentary by the recent editors of parts of the Greek alchemical corpus: Zosimos of Panopolis, *Mémoires authentiques*, ed. and tr. M. Mertens, Paris 1995; Pseudo-Democritus, *Scritti alchemici. Con il commentario di Sinesio*, ed. and tr. M. Martelli, Paris and Milan 2011, published in an updated English translation as *The Four Books of Pseudo-Democritus*, ed. and tr. M. Martelli, Leeds 2013; *Stephanos von Alexandria und sein alchemistisches Werk*, ed. M. Papathanassiou, Athens 2017. For these and earlier interventions by J. L. Ideler, M. Berthelot and others, see A. M. Roberts, 'Framing a Middle Byzantine Alchemical Codex', *Dumbarton Oaks Papers*, LXXIII, 2019, pp. 69–102 (70–74).

5. G. Merianos and S. Sakorrafou, 'Μαρτυρίες περί αλχημείας στο Βυζάντιο σε μη αλχημικά κείμενα', in

Επιστήμη και Τεχνολογία. Ιστορικές και ιστοριογραφικές μελέτες, ed. E. Mergoupe-Sabaidou et al., Athens 2013, pp. 45–65; G. Merianos, 'Alchemy', in *The Cambridge Intellectual History of Byzantium*, ed. A. Kaldellis and N. Siniossoglou, Cambridge 2017, pp. 234–51. For alchemy as part of ongoing scientific contacts between Byzantine and Arabophone scholars, see M. Mavroudi, *A Byzantine Book on Dream Interpretation: The Oneirocriticon of Achmet and Its Arabic Sources*, Leiden 2002, pp. 400–03. For alchemy as something 'occult' or 'ineffable' in Byzantine culture, see P. Magdalino and M. Mavroudi, 'Introduction', in *The Occult Sciences in Byzantium*, ed. P. Magdalino and M. Mavroudi, Geneva 2006, pp. 11–37 (18). On the Byzantine reception of Zosimos of Panopolis and the author called Stephen of Alexandria, see M. Mertens, 'Graeco-Egyptian Alchemy in Byzantium', *ibid.*, pp. 205–30; M. Papathanassiou, 'Stephanos of Alexandria: A Famous Byzantine Scholar, Alchemist and Astrologer', *ibid.*, pp. 163–203. On the question of Stephen of Alexandria's identity, see Roberts (as in n. 4), p. 71 n. 17, with references. Recent overviews include C. Viano, 'Byzantine Alchemy, or the Era of Systematization', in *Oxford Handbook of Science and Medicine in the Classical World*, ed. P. Keyser and J. Scarborough, Oxford 2018, pp. 943–64; V. Koutalis, M. Martelli and G. Merianos, 'Graeco-Egyptian, Byzantine and Post-Byzantine Alchemy: Introductory Remarks', in *Greek Alchemy from Late Antiquity to Early Modernity*, ed. E. Nicolaidis, Turnhout 2018, pp. 11–43.

6. Diktyon 69770. Described (in order of the present-day arrangement of quires) by E. Mioni, *Thesaurus antiquus, codices 1–299*, in *Bibliothecae Divi Marci Venetiarum codices graeci manuscripti*, I, Rome 1981, pp. 427–33. The original order of quires was reconstructed, based on the manuscript's table of contents, by H.-D. Saffrey, 'Historique et description du manuscrit alchimique de Venise Marcianus Graecus

speak of the Greek alchemical corpus, they are referring to a hypothetical set of texts most of which are in M.⁷ Several other, later manuscripts contain these texts (as well as other ones); and, according to some textual critics, not all of those manuscripts are ultimately dependent on M.⁸ Nevertheless, M is generally agreed to be our single most important witness to the corpus. Several alchemical papyri from much earlier survive,⁹ but they contain a different set of texts. Other manuscripts contain later texts not found in M, but because scholars, working in the long shadow cast by Marcellin Berthelot (1827–1907), have tended to concentrate on reconstructing ancient rather than Byzantine alchemy,¹⁰ M has remained the basis for most scholarly work on Greek alchemy. Better understanding of the social and cultural context of this manuscript's production and readership will interest not only Byzantinists but also historians and textual critics of ancient alchemy who, for better or for worse, must view their objects of study almost entirely through the lens of the medieval tradition.

M, as a codicological and compositional whole, fits well within elite middle Byzantine book culture, with its taste for ambitious, universal theories manifested in compendious tomes.¹¹ But at the same time, its structure is too loose to be closely associated with the best known set of Byzantine compilations: those produced at the court of Constantine VII Porphyrogenitus (905–59; r. 945–59). For example, while the Constantinian *Historical Excerpts* were produced by systematically excerpting a long list of earlier historical works and then rearranging the excerpts thematically,¹² M collects a mix of excerpts and integral texts in an order (following Henri-Dominique Saffrey's reconstruction) with discernible clusters but no unambiguous organisational scheme.¹³

In the present article, I will consider how a single page from this manuscript might further help us to pin down the elusive Byzantine reader of alchemical texts. That page, folio 5^v, contains a dedicatory epigram for the volume (Fig. 1). Although the margins of the page were subsequently filled by a late Byzantine scribe with an excerpt from the *Geoponika* on meteorological prognostication,¹⁴ the epigram

299', in *Alchimie: Art, histoire et mythes*, ed. D. Kahn and S. Matton, Paris and Milan 1995, pp. 1–10.

7. For M's contents, see Roberts (as in n. 4), §2, esp. pp. 88–90.

8. Martelli's edition of Pseudo-Democritus, for example, argues that several manuscripts along with M are mutually independent (with contamination): Pseudo-Democritus, *Scritti alchemici* (as in n. 4), pp. 3–54. For alternative views, with references, see Roberts (as in n. 4), pp. 75–76 and n. 54.

9. Most notably the papyri of Stockholm and Leiden: *Papyrus de Leyde. Papyrus de Stockholm. Fragments de recettes*, ed. and tr. R. Halleux, Paris 1981.

10. But see the relatively recent critical editions of later texts: *L'Anonyme de Zuretti, ou: L'art sacré et divin de la chrysope par un anonyme*, ed. and tr. A. Colinet, Paris 2000, esp. pp. VII and XII–XIV; *Recette alchimiques (Par. gr. 2419; Holkhamicus 109). Cosmas le*

Hiéromoine: Chrysope, ed. and tr. A. Colinet, Paris 2010, esp. pp. VII–VIII and CVII–CVIII.

11. Roberts (as in n. 4), §3, pp. 101–02.

12. A. Németh, 'The Imperial Systematisation of the Past in Constantinople: Constantine VII and his *Historical Excerpts*', in *Encyclopaedism from Antiquity to the Renaissance*, ed. J. König and G. Woolf, Cambridge 2013, pp. 232–58; idem, *The Excerpta Constantiniana and the Byzantine Appropriation of the Past*, Cambridge 2018.

13. Roberts (as in n. 4), §§2–3, esp. pp. 94–102.

14. *Geoponika*, 1.2–5, ed. H. Beckh, Leipzig 1895, pp. 6–10. See Mioni (as in n. 6), p. 428, no. 8; he dates this marginal addition to the 14th century but does not mention that after the excerpt ends, the very last words on the page are the heading for *Geoponika*, 1.7, which is the section with which the excerpt in the margin of the facing page begins. That excerpt (as mentioned by Mioni) is *Geoponika*, 1.7.1–11.5 (ed.

originally stood entirely alone, with no title or marginal annotation. Indeed, the only indication that the epigram begins on this page is the diamond of four dots at the beginning of the first line. The last line is not distinguished with any final mark, other than the single dot with which most other lines end. Three of the epigram's lines have been singled out by tildas in the left margin, apparently in the same hand and ink.¹⁵

The alchemical epigram appears in the manuscript's present-day first quire, along with other 'front matter', including the table of contents for the volume, a list of alchemical authors, and a table of symbols for metals and technical terms.¹⁶ In the present arrangement of that initial quire, the epigram faces the first page of the table of symbols.¹⁷

The epigram was first printed in 1745 as an appendix to Johannes Stephanus Bernard's edition of Palladius, *De febribus*.¹⁸ In the late nineteenth century, it was republished with a French prose translation by Berthelot and Charles-Émile Ruelle.¹⁹ In 1995, it was translated into French verse by Saffrey.²⁰ Here I offer my own edition and translation:

<p>2 Τὴν βίβλον ὄλβον ὥσπερ ἐγκεκρυμμένον ἔχουσαν ἄθρει τήνδε, πᾶς Μουσῶν φίλος. 4 Ἄλλ' εἰ θελήσεις τὰς πολυχρύσους φλέβας ταύτης ἐρευνᾶν τὰς σοφῶς κεκρυμμένας 6 νοῶς τὸ φαιδρὸν ὄμμα πρὸς θείας φύσεις ὑψεῖ διάρας πανσόφοις εὐοπτίαις οὕτω γραφὴν διελθε τὴν σοφωτάτην, 8 καὶ πλοῦτον εὐρησ γνῶσεως ὑπερτέρας ζητῶν, ἐρευνῶν τὴν τρισολβίαν φύσιν, 10 μόνην φύσεις νικῶσαν, ἐνθέῳ τρόπῳ, καὶ χρυσὸν αἰγλήεντα τίκτουσαν μόνην, 12 τὴν παντοποιόν, ἣν φρεσὶν μουσοστόλοις θείας ἐρασταὶ γνῶσεως εὖρον μόνοι. 14 Ταύτην ἐφευρὼν (μὴ γὰρ ὅστις ἦ φράσω) θαύμαζε νοῦν φρόνησιν ἀνδρῶν ἐνθέων, 16 ὡς δημιουργῶν σωμάτων καὶ πνευμάτων, πῶς ἔσχον οὕτως γνῶσεως ὕψος μέγα 18 ψυχῶν, ἀποκτένει τε καὶ ζωοῦν πάλιν, ὥστε ξένως πλάττειν τε καὶ μορφοῦν ξένως. 20 Ὡ θαῦμα, τὴν ἄνασσαν ὕλην ὀλβίαν! ἥσπερ διαγνοῦς καὶ μαθὼν τὰς ἐκβάσεις 22 αἰνιγματωδῶς ἐνδον ἐγκεκρυμμένας, ὁ νοῦς ὁ παγγέραστος, αἱ κλειναὶ φρένες, 24 Θεοδώρου πλουτοῦντος ἐνθέοις τρόποις πιστοῦ τελοῦντος δεσποτῶν παραστάτου 26 συνήψεν, ἐντέθεικε συλλογὴν ξένην ἐν τῇδε βίβλῳ πανσόφων νοημάτων, 28 ὄνπερ σκέπων φύλαττε, Χριστὲ παντάναξ.</p>	<p>(This book containing bliss, hidden as it were— gaze upon it, every Muses' friend! But should you wish its gold-rich veins to probe, so wisely hidden, then lift your mind's bright eye towards godly natures, to the peak, by all-wise splendours, and scrutinise this way the wisest writing, and you will find a wealth of higher knowledge as you seek and search for the thrice-happy nature that alone vanquishes natures in a god-inspired way and alone begets dazzling gold and makes everything; with their Muse-decorated wits, lovers of divine knowledge alone have found it. When you discover this nature (for let me not say who it is), wonder at the mind, the thought, of god-inspired men, for they are demiurges of bodies and spirits, at how they thus acquired the peak of knowledge, to endow with a soul, to kill and to give life again, so as strangely to fashion and strangely to mould. O what a marvel: the queen blessed matter! Discerning and learning her transformations, hidden enigmatically within, the mind renowned by all, the famous wits, of Theodore, rich in god-inspired ways, being a faithful companion of lords, put together a strange collection, placed it in this book of all-wise thoughts; protect and defend him, Christ, king of all!)</p>
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Apparatus criticus: 5 πρὸς] προς (no accent) M || 8 εὐρης] εὐρης M : εὔροις Berthelot || 10 τρόπῳ] τρόποι M || 11 terminal punctuation before μόνην M || 12 φρεσὶν] φ'ρ'εσὶν M || 14 ἦ] ἦ M on top of a scraped patch of parchment shaped in such a way as to suggest that the scribe may have originally written an εἰ-ligature (i.e., the homophonous εἰ, meaning 'for let me not say who you are') and then corrected it || 18 ἀποκτένειν] read -κτένειν or -κτείνειν || καὶ] (καὶ) M || 19 καὶ] (καὶ) M || ἐνθέοις τρόποις] originally ἐνθέους τρόπους in M before the right side of each υ was scraped away || 28 Χριστὲ] χ(ριστ)έ M.

1. Theodore

The alchemical epigram clearly names its patron: Theodore, praised for his ‘famous wits’ (‘κλειναὶ φρένες’, line 23). His good character was ‘god-inspired’ (‘ἐνθέοις τρόποις’, line 24), and he was a loyal companion of the powerful (‘πιστοῦ ... δεσποτῶν παραστάτου’, line 25).²¹ The epigram also makes clear that Theodore was responsible for the compilation of the book for which it was written.²² His good traits, the epigram implies, led Theodore to ‘put together ... a collection’ of texts ‘in this book’—presumably in the sense that he had someone else put it together. Alternatively, perhaps Theodore assembled the materials for the manuscript’s compilation and commissioned the fair copy that is M. Either way, in light of some of the sentiments expressed in the alchemical epigram, it seems unlikely that Theodore was its author.²³

High-end Byzantine manuscripts were often supplied with a dedicatory epigram, where the book’s scribe, author, compiler, donor or commissioner could address the reader, thank a patron or otherwise comment on the contents and physical manifestation of the book at hand.²⁴ The alchemical epigram is comparable to other epigrams for commissioners, such as the one in an eleventh-century Vatican manuscript about the Evangelists and the bishop Nicholas who gathered them together into a book.²⁵ In that example, too, one could theoretically imagine that Nicholas had penned the epigram himself, but such a hypothesis would likewise make Nicholas unusually excessive in praise for himself.²⁶

Beckh, pp. 11–21). (Beckh’s apparatus on p. 11 notes that one manuscript, the 13th-century *Anthologia Marciana* [Venice, Biblioteca Nazionale Marciana MS gr. 524; diktyon 69995] omits *Geoponika*, 1.6 in its excerpt from this part of the work [fols 190–92, written by the main scribe of the manuscript, who otherwise concentrated almost entirely on the poetry collected in this volume], so the 14th-century scribe may have copied a single continuous excerpt into M from an exemplar that was also missing this section. See E. Mioni, *Thesaurus antiquus, codices 300–625*, in *Bibliothecae Divi Marci Venetiarum codices graeci manuscripti*, II, Rome 1985, pp. 399–407, esp. 399 ¶5 and 407 no. XIX.) On M, fol. 5^r (the obverse of the folio on which the dedicatory epigram appears), the same hand copied various excerpts (described by Mioni) on dream interpretation, exegesis of the Psalms, numerology (isopsephy), etc.

15. Lines 9, 14 and 20, all directly concerned with the special sort of matter that is the epigram’s central technical theme.

16. The manuscript as currently bound is jumbled with respect to its original order as reconstructed by Saffrey (as in n. 6); for objections to his reconstruction and my attempt to answer those objections, see Roberts (as in n. 4), pp. 76–83. This has led some to question whether the ‘front matter’ was not perhaps originally at the end of the manuscript. I find it more plausible to envision these pages at or near the start of the original manuscript in light of other middle

Byzantine manuscripts (see *ibid.*, pp. 83–85); but for the present purposes, whether the epigram was placed at the front or the back is immaterial.

17. For a more detailed codicological account, see *ibid.*, pp. 76–78.

18. Palladius, *De febribus*, ed. Johannes Stephanus Bernard, Leiden 1745, pp. 149–50; cited in *CAAG*, II, p. 3.

19. *CAAG*, II, pp. 3–4; tr. III, pp. 3–4.

20. Saffrey (as in n. 6), p. 8.

21. The pre-caesura portions of these two lines rhyme: ‘Θεοδώρου πλουτοῦντος’, ‘πιστοῦ τελοῦντος’. This serves to emphasise two traits, his wealth (even if in spiritual riches) and loyalty, as a closely associated pairing. Perhaps the poet intended to encourage Theodore’s generosity.

22. As observed by Bernard in his edition of Palladius (as in n. 18), p. 150: ‘Videtur nomen esse illius, qui scriptores hos collegit ac in unum corpus congegessit.’

23. Lines 23–24, for example, would be rather boorish to write about oneself. See also above, n. 21 and below, n. 26.

24. K. Bentein and K. Demoen, ‘The Reader in Eleventh-Century Book Epigrams’, in *Poetry and Its Contexts in Eleventh-Century Byzantium*, ed. F. Bernard and K. Demoen, Farnham 2012, pp. 69–88.

25. BAV MS gr. 1650 (AD 1037; diktyon 68281), fols 185^v–186^r; ed. and tr. with discussion by Bentein and Demoen (as in n. 24), pp. 78–80.

Several opinions about this Theodore's identity, and so also the time at which he lived and the date when the epigram was composed, have been advanced in the literature. A recurring proposition is that he could be the Theodore whom Stephen of Alexandria's alchemical work addresses, thus placing him in the seventh century and making him a contemporary of Heraclius. Variants of this view are that he may be identified with Emperor Heraclius's brother Theodore; or with the Theodore to whom Zosimos's *Chapters to Theodore* are addressed.²⁷

'Theodore' is, however, an extremely common Byzantine name, so on its own it is of little use for dating the patron of the compilation.²⁸ Already in the 1930s, Frank Sherwood Taylor doubted the identification of the epigram's Theodore with Stephen of Alexandria's addressee, but his alternative suggestion, that the epigram is contemporary with the four iambic poems in M, which were then considered likely to date from the eighth century, cannot be right. Apart from the fact that these poems have since been convincingly dated much earlier, to the fifth or sixth century, Taylor's proposal ignores the close relationship between the epigram and the selection of texts it urges the reader to explore.²⁹

I propose that we reconsider this relationship as follows. We know that the epigram's Theodore commissioned a compilation that is contemporary with the epigram; that much we can gather from the epigram itself. If that compilation was

26. *Ibid.*, p. 79 n. 44. Bentein and Demoen cite K. Treu, 'Griechische Schreibernotizen als Quelle für politische, soziale und kulturelle Verhältnisse ihrer Zeit', *Byzantinobulgarica*, II, 1966, pp. 127–43, who observes that although judging whether a poem was written by or about someone can be somewhat subjective, from Byzantine scribes one typically expects humility about themselves but praise and honorific titles for those who commissioned their work (p. 139).

27. Berthelot, in *CAAG*, III, p. 4, observed that Theodore must have lived sometime between Heraclius (7th century) and M itself (10th or 11th), and suggested that he could be the Theodore addressed by Stephen of Alexandria. Saffrey (as in n. 6), pp. 8–9, citing line 25, 'πιστοῦ τελοῦντος δεσποτῶν παραστάτου', suggested that the epigram's Theodore might be identified with Heraclius's brother Theodore, further speculating that this Theodore was also Stephen of Alexandria's addressee. Mertens, in her edition of Zosimos of Panopolis (as in n. 4), p. LXI, maintains that we can at least conclude from this line that Theodore was probably a high-ranking courtier. She then (p. LXII) advances the hypothesis that the Theodore to whom Zosimos's *Chapters to Theodore* are addressed might be the same as both the Theodore of the dedicatory epigram and of Stephen of Alexandria's *Letter to Theodore*. To make this identification, she suggests that the text entitled 'Ζωσίμου πρὸς Θεόδωρον κεφάλαια' (M, no. 34, fol. 179^v) might in fact be a collection of excerpts from Zosimos which was compiled for Theodore, rather than a work addressed by Zosimos to someone by that name. Mertens (pp.

LXI–LXII) interprets both Theodore and Eusebeia, another addressee of Zosimos in the corpus, as patrons of abridgements of works, whose names thus became associated with these abridgements as addressees.

28. Or even for identifying a patron once a date has been established: every elite Theodore we may know of, especially from the middle Byzantine period, must have had various similarly distinguished contemporaries by the same name who have left no trace in the historical record. There are 267 entries for people named 'Theodoros' from the period 867–1025 in the *Prosopographie der mittelbyzantinischen Zeit*, Berlin 1998–2013, nos 27617–883. The name occurs frequently in earlier centuries as well: in the same reference work, there are 498 entries for 'Theodoros' from the period 641–867 (*ibid.*, nos 7290–787); and in *The Prosopography of the Later Roman Empire*, ed. A. H. M. Jones, J. R. Martindale and J. Morris, 3 vols, Cambridge 1971–92, there are 208 entries for 'Theodoros' from AD 527–641 (III, pp. 1243–90), 64 from AD 395–527 (II, pp. 1085–99), and 27 from AD 260–395 (I, pp. 896–902). Berthelot, in *CAAG*, III, p. 4, also observed that Theodore is a very common name.

29. F. S. Taylor, 'The Alchemical Works of Stephanos of Alexandria: Part II', *Ambix*, II, 1938, pp. 39–49 (46 n. 72). For the 8th-century date see R. Reitzenstein, 'Zur Geschichte der Alchimie und des Mystizismus', *Nachrichten von der Königlichen Gesellschaft der Wissenschaften zu Göttingen, Philologisch-historische Klasse*, 1919, pp. 1–37 (28); and G. Goldschmidt, in his edition of Heliodorus, *Carmina quattuor ad fidem codicis casselani*, Giessen 1923, pp. 16–21. For the earlier dating see below, n. 88.

identical to M's, then it included two texts extant in M that, as Jean Letrouit has pointed out, refer explicitly to Arabic terminology and so must postdate the Arab conquest and the development of Arabic alchemy; this, along with the excerpts from Agatharchides taken from Photius's *Bibliotheca*, places the compilation contained in M—and its patron—in the ninth century at the earliest.³⁰ In this scenario, still assuming Theodore's compilation was identical to M's, either the compilation was original to M or it was copied *in toto*, including the epigram, from a single exemplar. If, on the other hand, the compilation was not identical to M's, then the scribe of M drew the epigram and a subset of texts from one exemplar, supplementing it with texts from at least one other exemplar.

In theory this leaves open scenarios in which the epigram was copied into M from an earlier exemplar, rather than composed for M itself, such that the collection to which the epigram refers would be different from and much older than the collection contained in M. Yet such scenarios seem unnecessarily complicated, given that the epigram fits so well with the manuscript's contents. They also seem to derive from a sense that the manuscript's table of contents in the same quire does not match the manuscript well, an intuition dating from before Saffrey's convincing reconstruction of the original order of the quires. Even Saffrey, who argued that the table of contents was almost a perfect match for the actual contents, once one accounted for a later loss and misbinding of quires, still thought that the excerpts from Agatharchides on the last extant pages of the manuscript (in the reconstructed order) were not accounted for.³¹ But these extracts may have been understood by the drafter of the table of contents as part of the 'other chapters' (ἕτερα κεφάλαια) referred to in the last line: this entry corresponds to excerpts originally placed at the end of the manuscript, of which the last are the Agatharchides extracts.³²

It is not uncommon for a deluxe middle Byzantine manuscript to bear an epigram dedicating it to its commissioner.³³ It would have been odd for such a high-quality manuscript to be produced and then inscribed not to its patron but rather with an epigram addressing someone else. Moreover, while many of the texts included in M are avowedly older than the manuscript itself, there is nothing to suggest that this particular assembly of texts, or the alchemical epigram, pre-dates M. That previous scholars have tended to think that it did may be a result of a fading, though still lingering, tendency to see medieval Byzantium as a stage of transmission, or at most of systematisation,³⁴ but not of genuine creativity. Only relatively recently have scholars of Byzantine literature taught us to expect to find poetry and literary creation among the Byzantines,³⁵ prompting the salutary

30. J. Letrouit, 'Chronologie des alchimistes grecs', in *Alchimie* (as in n. 6), pp. 11–93 (65–68). See also *ODB*, s.v. 'Photios' and 'Bibliotheca'. For the two Arabic recipes as evidence of Byzantine reception of Arabic alchemy, see Mavroudi (as in n. 5), 401–02.

31. Saffrey (as in n. 6), pp. 6–7.

32. M, no. 52. See Letrouit (as in n. 30), pp. 66–68; and Roberts (as in n. 4), §2, esp. p. 99 and n. 180.

33. M. Lauxtermann, *Byzantine Poetry from Pisides to Geometres*, 2 vols, Vienna 2003–19, I, pp. 197–200, 206–12. For the 11th century see Bentein and Demoen (as in n. 24), pp. 70, 78–80.

34. For this characterisation see Viano (as in n. 5).

35. See M. Mullett, 'No Drama, No Poetry, No Fiction, No Readership, No Literature', in *A Companion to Byzantium*, ed. L. James, Chichester

re-evaluation of the intellectual and ideological purposes of middle Byzantine compilation.³⁶ M's collection as it now stands must date from the ninth century (Photius) to around the tenth or eleventh century (M itself). Why not the epigram as well?

2. Metre

It would help if we could date the epigram on internal criteria. The precise nature of its dodecasyllable metre is one such criterion that can now be analysed with the help of the detailed *appendix metrica* in Marc Lauxtermann's second volume on *Byzantine Poetry*.³⁷ The dodecasyllable metre developed out of the ancient iambic trimetre. As the Greek language transitioned from quantity-based to stress-based, a process completed by the ninth century, the iambic trimetre, which Byzantine poets continued to use, was gradually transformed into a stress-based metre preserving some characteristics such as a line-length of about twelve syllables (which became exactly twelve syllables in the isosyllabic Byzantine version) and a caesura after the fifth or seventh syllable, but also including new ones such as the tendency to stress the second-to-last syllable of the line (paroxytone), which eventually became a requirement.³⁸ The alchemical epigram's metre is stress-based but also attentive to quantity, in that the lines all scan as iambic trimetre of the Byzantine sort.³⁹ This tells us that the poet was highly educated but does not help much with the date because long after the Greek language had ceased to differentiate long and short vowels, and throughout the Byzantine period, learned poets made a point of following the old prosody to a certain extent. But features of the stress-accentuation found in the epigram—to which Byzantine ears were finely attuned—turn out to be much more helpful.

First of all, line-endings. Stress accentuation at the ends of lines in Byzantine poetry, especially early Byzantine poetry, can be proparoxytone (on the third-to-last syllable), paroxytone (on the second-to-last syllable) or even sometimes oxytone (on the final syllable), but paroxytone is generally preferred. Oxytones and proparoxytones dwindle from uncommon in the seventh century (George of Pisidia's later work) to extremely rare in the ninth and tenth centuries; in the eleventh and

2010, pp. 227–38; A. Kazhdan, *A History of Byzantine Literature*, 2 vols, Athens 1999–2006; Lauxtermann (as in n. 33).

36. See, e.g., Németh, *Excerpta Constantiniana* (as in n. 12).

37. Lauxtermann (as in n. 34), II, pp. 265–383.

38. *ODB*, s.v. 'Dodecasyllable'; Lauxtermann (as in n. 34), II, pp. 284–304, 320–23, 326–28. Whereas 'resolution' (two shorts in place of one long) and 'anapaestic substitution' (two shorts and a long instead of one short and a long) was still relatively frequent in the 4th century, after George of Pisidia (7th century, panegyrist of Emperor Heraclius), Byzantine poetry in iambic trimetre was typically isosyllabic (meaning that it kept strictly to 12 syllables), since it ruled out resolution and anapaestic substitutions: *ibid.*, II, p. 288.

39. For Byzantine practices in composing prosodic iambic trimetre (and other metres), see Lauxtermann (as in n. 34), II, pp. 269–84. Contrast, in particular, Lauxtermann's schema for the Byzantine iambic trimetre (p. 269) with the schema in P. Maas, *Greek Metre*, tr. H. Lloyd-Jones, Oxford 1962, p. 66 (§101). In line 18 of the alchemical epigram, the penultimate syllable of the word ἀποκτέννειν has been shortened by changing the double-*nu* to a single *nu*: ἀποκτένειν. Although it is not unknown to replace double letters with single letters for metrical reasons (Lauxtermann, *ibid.*, p. 279, gives two examples, one from John Geometres, the other from Theodore Prodromos), the syllable in question is the fifth, which is anceps (i.e., either long or short), so this does not seem to be a case of metrical adjustment; it is probably a scribal error.

twelfth centuries, paroxytone has become the firm rule, with very few exceptions.⁴⁰ It is therefore telling that all twenty-eight line-endings in the alchemical epigram have paroxytone stress accentuation. This would tend to place the epigram in the tenth or eleventh century, although it would also be consistent with a somewhat earlier date.⁴¹

Byzantine dodecasyllables also display certain patterns of accentuation before the caesura.⁴² In the alchemical epigram, fifteen lines have a caesura after the fifth syllable (C5); the other thirteen have it after the seventh (C7). Among the C5 lines, the accentuation before the caesura is oxytone in seven (forty-seven percent) and paroxytone in eight (fifty-three percent). Among the C7 lines, it is paroxytone in four (thirty-one percent) and proparoxytone in nine (sixty-nine percent).⁴³ Particularly striking is the total avoidance of proparoxytones before C5, and of oxytones before C7. If we compare this to Lauxtermann's data on the dodecasyllables of the Byzantine poets he examined, covering the period from George of Pisidia to Theodosios the Deacon (tenth century),⁴⁴ we find that the lack of oxytones before C7 is not informative as to date, because very low frequency or total avoidance of oxytones before C7 was the general rule. The absence of proparoxytones before C5, however, is very revealing. Lauxtermann's data show consistently non-negligible rates of proparoxytones before C5: mostly around eight to twenty percent (though in one example under three percent).⁴⁵ Only after the tenth century did Lauxtermann find that some poets avoided proparoxytones before C5 entirely.⁴⁶ This strongly suggests that the alchemical epigram in M was written in the tenth century or later.⁴⁷

Twenty-eight lines is, unfortunately, too small a sample to establish the epigram's metrical fingerprint and *terminus post quem* beyond a doubt. Still, in light of what we know about the epigram and the manuscript so far, it shifts the

40. Lauxtermann (as in n. 33), II, pp. 320–22; these figures do not include intentionally classicising verse or sustained imitations of Euripides (which are thus also not strictly isosyllabic), nor do they include poets who were simply sloppy in their versifying.

41. Lauxtermann measured very low rates of deviation from paroxytone line-endings for as early as the 9th century, when Theodore the Studite deviated from them in 0.6% of his extant verse: at this rate, there is an 84% chance that 28 lines would yield no deviations. The 8th century is somewhat less plausible: Andrew of Crete (d. 740) deviated from paroxytones in 3.9% of his extant lines, at which rate 28 lines would yield no deviations only 33% of the time.

42. *Ibid.*, pp. 326–28.

43. Using Lauxtermann's abbreviations, the line-by-line pre-caesura accentuation of the alchemical epigram is: 1 (5p), 2 (7p), 3 (5p), 4 (5ox), 5 (7p), 6 (5p), 7 (7pp), 8 (5p), 9 (5ox), 10 (7p), 11 (7pp), 12 (5ox), 13 (5ox), 14 (5ox), 15 (7pp), 16 (5ox), 17 (5p), 18 (7pp), 19 (7pp), 20 (7pp), 21 (5ox), 22 (5p), 23 (7pp), 24 (7p), 25 (5p), 26 (7pp), 27 (5p), 28 (7pp).

44. Lauxtermann (as in n. 33), II, pp. 327–28.

45. That example, *Encomium on a Calabrian Youth* (86 lines), nonetheless diverges subtly but perceptibly from the alchemical epigram in other ways: before C5, it is oxytone in 52.5% of lines, paroxytone in 45% and proparoxytone in 2.5%; before C7, it is oxytone in 0%, paroxytone in 19% and proparoxytone in 81%. The *Encomium* is known from a manuscript copied in 1317, but a 30-verse version appears in a 10th-century manuscript; see *ibid.*, I, pp. 47–48.

46. *Ibid.*, II, p. 327. Lauxtermann's examples of poets who avoid proparoxytones before C5 range from the 11th to the 14th century.

47. The epigram's use of rhyme before the caesura in lines 24–25 (see above, n. 21) further corroborates this. Lauxtermann (as in n. 33), I, pp. 145–47, in his analysis of an epitaph for Leo the Philosopher (or, the Mathematician) by Leo's student, Leo Choirosphaktes, distinguishes between classicising epigrams and epigrams that derive their style and referents from Byzantine rhetoric and poetry. One feature that he identifies as particularly Byzantine, rather than ancient, is the use of rhyme before the caesura in two successive lines.

preponderance of the evidence to supporting the hypothesis that the alchemical epigram was not copied into M from an earlier compilation (especially not a seventh-century compilation) but was produced to celebrate the production of M itself and to frame and build expectations for its contents.

3. Palaeography

Assigning M to a single century on palaeographical grounds has so far proved elusive: the minuscule of the main scribe has been dated variously to between the early tenth and the twelfth century.⁴⁸ The manuscript contains two variants of this minuscule, of which the first, used for the main text, is relatively plain and was executed in a brown ink (Fig. 3).⁴⁹ The second, used for the alchemical epigram and also to label some drawings of laboratory equipment, is a more ornamented *minuscule bouletée*, executed in a reddish ink (Figs 1 and 2).⁵⁰ This same reddish ink is used for semi-uncials on the rest of the extant original pages of the initial quire that includes the epigram. The two variants share many features but are noticeably distinct, most obviously in the uniform thickness of the first variant's strokes and the absence of ornamental hooks and balls at the ends of its strokes.

It has been pointed out to me that the page in M bearing the alchemical epigram is palaeographically quite similar to two luxurious tenth-century manuscripts: Berlin, Staatsbibliothek [hereafter: BSB] MS gr. 134, the oldest witness to the *Hippiatrica*, and Vatican City, Biblioteca Apostolica Vaticana [hereafter: BAV] MS Barb. gr. 310, the so-called *Anthologia Barberina*.⁵¹ A sample of the minuscule used in BSB gr. 134 makes clear the similarity of the script to that of the epigram, not only in overall appearance and general characteristics but also in the details of letter forms and ligatures (Figs 1 and 4).⁵² While not strictly identical in every

48. See Roberts (as in n. 4), p. 75 n. 46, where I cite the palaeographical judgements reported by Mioni, *Thesaurus antiquus, codices 1–299* (as in n. 6), p. 427; Mertens, in her edition of Zosimos of Panopolis (as in n. 4), p. XXII; and Mavroudi (as in n. 5), p. 107 n. 50. See also I. Pérez Martín, 'Byzantine Books', in *The Cambridge Intellectual History of Byzantium* (as in n. 5), pp. 37–46 (45 n. 36), dating the hand (without explanation) to the beginning of the tenth century. She also describes its script as 'bouletée', suggesting that her description is restricted to the alchemical epigram, since most of the manuscript is written in a script that lacks the characteristic *boules* at the ends of strokes (though it shares many of the other key features of *bouletée* script).

49. M, fol. 8^r. This is the first page of the first text of the collection.

50. See the canonical description by J. Irigoien, 'Une écriture du X^e siècle: La minuscule bouletée', in *La paléographie grecque et byzantine*, ed. idem, J. Bompaire and J. Glénisson, Paris 1977, pp. 191–99; and further M. L. Agati, *La minuscola 'bouletée'*, pref. P. Canart, 2 vols, Vatican City 1992. The drawings in M with captions in *minuscule bouletée* are on fols 188^v (Fig. 2), 193^v, 194^v and 195^v–196^v.

51. I owe this crucial observation to an anonymous reviewer for this *Journal*. For BSB gr. 134 (diktyon 9439; often referred to as Phillipps 1538), see A. McCabe, *A Byzantine Encyclopaedia of Horse Medicine: The Sources, Compilation, and Transmission of the Hippiatrica*, Oxford 2007, pp. 23–27; and, further, n. 68 below. For BAV MS Barb. gr. 310 (diktyon 64853) see M. L. Agati, 'Su due manoscritti in bouletée «élancée»', *Byzantion*, LIV, 1984, pp. 615–25 (615–19); cited by C. Gallavotti, 'Note su testi e scrittori di codici greci', *Rivista di studi bizantini e neoellenici*, n.s., XXIV, 1987, pp. 29–83 (p. 31 n. 6); cited, in turn, by G. Cavallo, 'Qualche riflessione sulla continuità della cultura greca in Oriente tra i secoli VII e VIII', *Byzantinische Zeitschrift*, LXXXVIII, 1995, pp. 13–22 (18 n. 32). The main minuscules in these two manuscripts (as well as 'some features of their ornament') were judged identical by N. G. Wilson, *Scholars of Byzantium*, London 1983, p. 143; Wilson is cited by I. Pérez Martín, 'The Reception of Xenophon in Byzantium: The Macedonian Period', *Greek, Roman and Byzantine Studies*, LIII, 2013, pp. 812–55 (831 n. 56).

52. BSB gr. 134, fol. 7^v (Fig. 4). For example, the κ with a gap between its left and right strokes; the use of two forms of λ, one perched on the ruling (and

2. Venice, Biblioteca Nazionale Marciana MS gr. 299 (M), fol. 188v: alchemical equipment and other drawings, labelled using the *bouletée* form of the scribe's minuscule; a majuscule of the epigraphic type is used in the two concentric rings; the heading for this page is executed in semi-uncials of the Alexandrian type

3. Venice, Biblioteca Nazionale Marciana MS gr. 299 (M), fol. 85r: the first page of the first text of the alchemical corpus, lectures of 'Stephen of Alexandria', executed in the plain variant of the scribe's miniature

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aspect,⁵³ these are very similar hands. The situation is much the same when we compare the epigram to BAV Barb. gr. 310 (Fig. 5). Maria Luisa Agati, in her palaeographical account of that manuscript, provides a table of key characteristics of its main script.⁵⁴ Almost every feature she highlights as especially distinctive is to be found in the epigram as well.⁵⁵ Her systematic comparison and identification of the main script of BAV Barb. gr. 310 with that of a different BSB manuscript, gr. fol. 73,⁵⁶ which contains orations by Gregory of Nazianzus, is likewise telling (Fig. 6).⁵⁷ The unusual shared features that she highlights are also shared by the alchemical epigram.⁵⁸ Agati's clinching evidence in her identification of the main script of BAV Barb. gr. 310 and the script of BSB gr. fol. 73 is a comparison of the relative frequencies with which certain ligatures are used.⁵⁹ Since she was working with full codices rather than a single page, she was for the most part able to choose samples of a hundred instances of each pair of letters occurring within a word. That is, of course, impossible for the alchemical epigram, but performing the same analysis on it is nevertheless instructive, at least for the letter-pairs that appear more than once or twice. The results again point to a near-perfect match with these two manuscripts, perhaps especially BSB gr. fol. 73.⁶⁰

peculiarly broad), the other with its first stroke rising from below; the open-topped σ in the $\varepsilon\sigma$ ligature (compare the alchemical epigram's line 12, $\varphi\rho'\varepsilon\sigma\iota\nu$, with BSB line 7, $\acute{\alpha}\rho\acute{\epsilon}\sigma\kappa\alpha\iota$); the slightly left-leaning δ ; the form and curvature of the h-type η as well as the terminal $\eta\nu$ ligature; the precise form of the $\varepsilon\iota$ ligature; the disconnected execution of the letter-sequence $\upsilon\sigma$; and the shape of the $\varepsilon\nu$ ligature.

53. Whereas the alchemical epigram always uses the form of the φ used in BSB line 10, the BSB manuscript also employs a form of the same letter featuring a crossbar on the enclosed part of the vertical stroke; the descending and rising stroke on the BSB manuscript's ψ is perhaps slightly more angular at the bottom (like a 'v') than in the alchemical epigram (more like υ); and the abbreviation for $\kappa\alpha\iota$ on the last line of the BSB page does not appear in the alchemical epigram, though the 'S' form does, in lines 18 and 19 as part of a $\tau\epsilon$ - $(\kappa\alpha\iota)$ ligature.

54. Agati, 'Su due manoscritti' (as in n. 51), p. 620 (fig. 1).

55. Perhaps most strikingly the $\alpha\xi$ ligature (Agati 1d, alchemical epigram line 28 end) and two of the three different $\lambda\lambda$ ligatures (Agati 1c1, alchemical epigram line 26 $\sigma\upsilon\lambda\lambda\omicron\gamma\eta\nu$; Agati 1c2, alchemical epigram line 3 $\acute{\alpha}\lambda\lambda'\varepsilon\iota$; these are the only two instances of $\lambda\lambda$ in the epigram). The κ (Agati 1b2) is identical. The alchemical epigram's ψ (lines 6, 17, 18, 26) is slightly less angular than that of BAV Barb. gr. 310 (which is more like that of BSB gr. 134), but again, the differences are quite slight. Of the two abbreviations for $\kappa\alpha\iota$ that Agati lists, only Agati 1i1 appears (alchemical epigram lines 18 and 19).

56. For BSB gr. fol. 73 (diktyon 9163), see Agati, 'Su due manoscritti' (as in n. 51), pp. 619–21; and F.

Berger, 'Katalog einiger griechischer Handschriften aus dem Besitz der Staatsbibliothek Preußischer Kulturbesitz, erstellt während eines Praktikums in der Handschriftenabteilung im Herbst 2001', [Berlin] 2001, pp. 5–8. (Robert Giel at the Staatsbibliothek zu Berlin kindly provided me with a copy of the relevant entry from this unpublished catalogue.) Despite the word 'fol(io)' in its call number, this BSB manuscript's format is quarto; see Agati, p. 619.

57. Agati, 'Su due manoscritti' (as in n. 51), pp. 621–23.

58. In particular, $\lambda\lambda$, $\varepsilon\sigma$ with open sigma, and the seven letter forms listed in her fig. 2, all of which the alchemical epigram shares except the last, no. 7, namely the $\omicron\nu$ ligature at the ends of lines (presumably to ensure that a word fits within the ruling). Only one line of the alchemical epigram ends in $\omicron\nu$ (line 25), and it does not come close to the right-hand ruling, so it may well be that the scribe would have used this ligature elsewhere but saw no need to do so on this particular page.

59. Agati, 'Su due manoscritti' (as in n. 51), pp. 623–24.

60. Agati's table on p. 624 has a printer's error in the column labelled 'Tipologie': items 2–4 are upside-down and in an order that should be reversed; to correct the error, one must rotate the whole block of three items by 180 degrees. The letter combinations covered by the table are $\alpha\xi$, $\alpha\xi$, $\varepsilon\xi$, $\varepsilon\xi$, $\varepsilon\nu$, $\varepsilon\pi$, $\varepsilon\nu$ and $\upsilon\sigma$. In the alchemical epigram, $\varepsilon\xi$ and $\varepsilon\xi$ do not appear. Only a single form of each of $\alpha\xi$ and $\alpha\xi$ appears in BAV Barb. gr. 310 and BSB gr. fol. 73; the same respective forms appear once each in the alchemical epigram. For $\varepsilon\nu$, the single form used in BAV Barb. gr. 310 and BSB gr. fol. 73 appears 15 of 16 times (94%) in the

μυμοσ. τὸ πολὺ τὴσ ἐκ
 κλησίασ. διὰ τὴσ ἐκ
 διέφθαρτον. οὐτε τὸν
 πρῶτη μὴσασ. καὶ αὐ
 τιμάσασ τὰ ἐξ αὐτοῦ.
 διατόμαρ ἰσορροπιασ
 τὴσ θείότητος. ἀλλὰ
 μίαν μὲν δόξαν πρὸς γι
 μῶσιν οὐ μὲν. τὴν ὁμοτι
 μίαν τοῦ μορογέμουσ.
 μίαν δὲ τοῦ. τὴν τὸν
 πρῶσ. καὶ ὁ τὸν τρι
 ῶν καὶ αὐτῶ μὲν. τὸ πρῶ
 κατὰ τὸν ἴσον μίαν μὲν.
 τριῶν μὲν ταῖσιν ἰδίῳ τὴ
 σιγ. ἐν δὲ τὴσ θείότητι
 σίμω τὰσ καὶ γινώσκον
 τὰσ. ὡρὸν δὲ μὲν ὡρὸν
 ἐκ τῶσ. οὐδὲ αὐτῶσ τῶσ
 δυνάμεισ. ἀλλὰ ἰσο
 τῶσ ἴσων τῶσ αὐτῶσ

πρῶσ μὲν οὐσ. σὺν τῶ
 πρῶσ ἰσὼσ μὲν οὐ
 αὐτῶσ καὶ φῶσιν ἰσο
 τῶσ. καὶ ἰσομα γινώ
 ται πορὸν. ἴσων δὲ
 λῶσ καὶ αὐτῶσ τὴν
 δεσποτῶσ. καὶ μὲν αὐ
 τὴσ καὶ ἰσοσ τὴσ θεί
 τῶσ αὐτῶσ φῶσιν ἰ
 ἰσοσ χροσ. ὁ μὲν ἰσ
 οῦσ φροσ. καὶ μὲν αὐ
 τοῖσ τὴσ ἰσοσ τῶσ
 τῶσ τὴσ αὐτῶσ. οὐ
 γὰρ ἀλλοτῶσ. ἰσοσ
 ρεῖσ ἰσοσ αὐτῶσ μὲν
 τὸν τῶσ ἰσοσ τῶσ. κα
 τῶσ οὐσ αὐτῶσ οὐ
 ἰσοσ τῶσ καὶ ἰσοσ.
 οὐδὲ αὐτῶσ μὲν οὐσ
 χροσ ἰσοσ καὶ αὐ
 τῶσ οὐσ τῶσ μὲν οὐσ.

6. Berlin, Staatsbibliothek MS gr. fol. 73, fol. 103^r: sample of the main minuscule used for this manuscript

7. Venice, Biblioteca Nazionale Marciana MS gr. 299 (M), fol. 2v:
second page of the table of contents, in semi-uncials

Finally, we may briefly consider the other middle Byzantine scripts used in M. First, there are the semi-uncials employed in the rest of the front matter, for example, on the second page of the table of contents (Fig. 7).⁶¹ These semi-uncials are also found in most of the headings throughout the manuscript, for example, the one at the top of a page containing various drawings which, as indicated above, also contains labels executed in the same minuscule that was used for the alchemical epigram (Fig. 2).⁶² They are very similar to the semi-uncials used to execute the tables of contents in BAV Barb. gr. 310 (Fig. 8) and BSB gr. 134 (Fig. 9).⁶³ Moreover, these examples not only conform to the same palaeographic type;⁶⁴ they are quite similar in particular details. Second, it is instructive to compare the plain minuscule used in most of M with the more ornamented *bouletée* used in the alchemical epigram, BAV Barb. gr. 310, BSB gr. 134 and BSB gr. fol. 73. By good fortune, M and BSB gr. 134 share a text: excerpts from Cleopatra's *On Measures and Weights* ('ἡ μνᾶ ὄνομα ἔχει σταθμοῦ...');⁶⁵ this facilitates a comparison of the two scripts (Figs 10–11). Juxtaposing the two, we find that the *bouletée* in BSB gr. 134 is not only more ornamented than this plainer variant of the minuscule in M: its strokes are also more rounded, and the two scripts differ in various details.⁶⁶

alchemical epigram (lines 1, 4, 10, 11, 15, 19 twice, 22 twice, 23, 24, 26 three times, 27), but the disconnected form appears once (line 18 ἀποκτένειν [*sic*]); the one exception might be due to the same scribal lapse that resulted in an omitted letter at this point; perhaps the scribe paused mid-word (at the first ε) and then continued without realising that a letter (ι or ν) was missing. Finally, ετ, εν, and υσ each have two or three forms that appear in at least one of the manuscripts. επ¹ (C-shaped ε): BAV Barb. gr. 310, 68%; BSB gr. fol. 73, 100%; alchemical epigram, in the only use of this ligature (line 28, retraced at a later date). επ² (G-shaped ε): BAV Barb. gr. 310, 32%; BSB gr. fol. 73, 0%; alchemical epigram, none (see επ¹). ευ¹ (G-shaped ε): BAV Barb. gr. 310, 50%; BSB gr. fol. 73, 56%; alchemical epigram, four of seven uses of this ligature, or 57% (lines 6, 8, 13, 14). ευ² (disconnected): BAV Barb. gr. 310, 44.5%; BSB gr. fol. 73, 42%; alchemical epigram, the other three of seven uses of this ligature, or 43% (lines 4, 9, 16). ευ³ (ε with straight diagonal stroke): BAV Barb. gr. 310, 4.5%; BSB gr. fol. 73, 2%; alchemical epigram, none. υσ¹ (disconnected): BAV Barb. gr. 310, 88%; BSB gr. fol. 73, 100%; alchemical epigram, all 12 (2 twice, 3 twice, 5, 9, 10, 11 twice, 12, 21, 23; I have not counted the two instances on line 24 where it seems that an original -ους with υσ¹ was emended to -οις). υσ² (connected): BAV Barb. gr. 310, 12%; BSB gr. fol. 73, 0%; alchemical epigram, none (see υσ¹). Of these, the most telling are εν, where the alchemical epigram almost matches the other two manuscripts (especially if the one exception is excused); ευ, where the alchemical epigram matches the proportions appearing in BAV Barb. gr. 310, and BSB gr. fol. 73 quite well; and υσ, where the alchemical epigram matches BSB gr. fol. 73 best. To complete the

picture, see also M. L. Agati, 'Postilla al Barberinianus graecus 310', *Byzantion*, LV, 1985, pp. 584–88 (586 with fig. 1) (cited by Gallavotti, as in n. 52, p. 31 n. 6): here she enumerates the ways in which Hand B of BAV Barb. gr. 310 differs from Hand A, and shows that yet another manuscript, Patmos, Monastery of St John the Theologian MS gr. 163 (10th century, containing works of John Chrysostom; diktyon 54407) matches Hand B. For every feature she cites as especially telling, the alchemical epigram matches Hand A and contrasts with Hand B and the Patmos manuscript.

61. M, fol. 2^v.

62. M, fol. 188^v. See above, n. 51.

63. BAV Barb. gr. 310, fol. 1^v; BSB gr. 134, fol. 1^r.

64. This type of semi-uncial (*Auszeichnungsmajuskel*) conforms to the Alexandrian type described by J. Irigoien, 'L'onziale grecque de type copte', *Jahrbuch der Österreichischen Byzantinischen Gesellschaft*, VIII, 1959, pp. 29–51 (45); cited by H. Hunger, 'Minuskel und Auszeichnungsschriften im 10.–12. Jahrhundert', in *La paléographie grecque et byzantine* (as in n. 50), pp. 201–20 (205 n. 19); Hunger is cited in turn by Agati, 'Su due manoscritti' (as in n. 51), pp. 617 n. 12, 618. By contrast, the title on the first page of the alchemical corpus proper in M (Fig. 3) is executed in the 'epigraphic' type, discussed by Hunger, *ibid.*, p. 207. A different majuscle of the epigraphic type was used to fill the two concentric rings of one of the drawings on fol. 188^v (Fig. 2); see above, n. 50.

65. M, no. 46, fols 108^v, line 1, to 110^r, line 5; BSB gr. 134, fols 390^v–392^r. The shared portion begins at M, fol. 108^v, line 10; BSB gr. 134, fol. 390^v, line 4.

66. In BSB gr. 134, fol. 390^v, line 4, the στ-ligature features the left side of the τ protruding past the left side of the σ (in M, line 10, it does not); δ leans left,

ἜΙΣΤΟΝ ἈΓΙΟΝ ἸΩ Τὸν Θεοῦ:
 ἜΙΣΤΟΝ ἈΓ^ο Πρωτὸ στέφανο:
 ἜΙΣΤΗΝ ἈΓ^ο Πρωτὸ θεϊκλάν:
 ἜΙΣΤΗΝ Ἀλωστὰ γίας ποῦ:
 ἜΙΣ Ἐἄ^ο ἦτοι εἰς τὸν ἄεωτον:
 ἜΙΣ Τὸν ἁγίον Ἰσχυρὸν ἄγγυπτι:
 ἜΙΣ ΝΑΡΧΗΝ Εἰς τὸν ἄκαλῶν
 ἰς τὸν Δογματων
 ἜΙΣ Τὸν τίμων στρον:
 ἜΙΣ Τὸν ἀλὴν ψιν ἰς Ἐἄ^ο
 ἜΙΣ Τὸν ὄν ἔχεν ἑκαγία ἡ:
 Τὸ ἄγ^ο ἁμακρὸ κατὰ τοῖ
 εἰς τὸν παπ^ο τον μνηάν
 τον οἰκονόμον τ^ο ἐν ἡατ^ο
 ἀλεξανδρείας τυκοφαν
 τιθεῖν ἐπιφωκὰ ὅτι θεο
 δόσιος τὸν ἰόν μαυρισί
 ἰδέζατο:
 Τὸ ἄγ^ο ἁμακρὸ κατὰ τοῖ εἰς τ^ο

8. Vatican City, Biblioteca Apostolica Vaticana MS Barb. gr. 310, fol. 1^v,
second page of the table of contents, in semi-uncials

9. Berlin, Staatsbibliothek MS gr. 134, fol. 1r: first page of the table of contents, in semi-uncials

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: ΕΚ ΤΩ ΝΙΚΛΙΟ ΠΑΤΡΑΙ ΤΗ ΜΕΤΡΩΝ ΚΑΙ ΤΑΜΩΝ :

Π ⁺ βριμβρομα και ααθμομ βηπλαταξ ζήγησο προς
 βυχρη βύρεσημ. βικασησμασ. και λιτροσ ζοικί
 ασ. και δραχησικαι γραμματοσ. ποσσοσ δροσμο
 ωλοισ. και θερμοσ. και κβραττα. και χαλλωισ.
 :: βύοισ η λαποτησ του ααθμοβύτοισ διωαμδμοισ
 βύρισεται κβ μβν η η βύωσφαι μεαδβ τη μπουταμ
 λαποτητα και αδρομβροσ. βικασομ ααθμομ ιαπε
 τζα. ιμα και βύτω τβύα βύρισηηε τομ βητο
 μβνομ ααθμομ. Η μβασορομα δα ααθμομ. ε
 χαδβ το ις. δραχμασ δβ ρκη. γραμμαρια δβ τωβ
 οωλοισ δβ τζη. θερμοσ δβ αρμη 55 μβ. χαλ
 κοισ δβ 5 ρμβ. νομίσμα 45 :-
 Η αηλικη μβασ δα το ιω. δραχμασ ρ. γραμμαρια τ.
 οωλοισ χ. θερμοσ η 55 αω. χαλλκοισ δβ δω. νο
 μίσματα οε :-
 Η πολβμαϊκη μβασ δα το ιη. δραχμασ ρμβ. γραμ
 μαρια υλι. οωλοισ ωζα. θερμοσ αης. 55 μβ
 ηυ. χαλλωισ δβ 5 ηιβ. νομίσματα ρη :-
 Η λιτρα δα το ιυ. δραχμασ ης. γραμμαρια σπη. οω
 λοισ φος. θερμοσ ωζδ. 55 αητικη. χαλλωισ δβ
 δλη νομίσμασ. Η το δα δραχμασ η. γραμμαρια ικα.
 οωλοισ μη. θερμοσ ου. 55 ρμβ. χαλλωισ τωβ. νο
 μίσματα 5. καλ εταδβ η το τερασαριομ η γαλιωμ.
 Η δραχη δα γραμμαρια τ. οωλοισ 5. θερμοσ φ.
 55 ηη. χαλλκοισ μη. νομίσμα 5 ιη. το ιη γαλιωμ
 δημαριομ δα δραχηω α:
 δραχη δβ και αλλη νομίσμασ καλ ετα. ηαι γρατικη

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10. Venice, Biblioteca Nazionale Marciana MS gr. 299 (M), fol. 108^v: the excerpts from Cleopatra's *On Measures and Weights* begin at line 10 after a preface

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11. Berlin, Staatsbibliothek MS gr. 134, fol. 390^v: first page of the excerpts from Cleopatra's *On Measures and Weights*, in minuscule with ornamented heading

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(footnote 66, continued)

e.g., in lines 4, 5, 6 (vertical in M, lines 11–13); η is of the h-type with a single non-overlapping stroke that loops up after the initial vertical drop then loops down again, e.g., lines 4, 7 (M uses the H-type, e.g., lines 10, 11, 12, 14); γ is curved and loops at the bottom, e.g., lines 4, 7, 9 (in M, lines 11, 14, 17, it is angular like

a 'V'); and the initial stroke of μ frequently does not drop down, e.g., lines 4–5 (in M it usually does, lines 10–16); even though the two scripts share features like the hook at the bottom of ρ, the gap between the two strokes of κ, the broad λ, and a τπ-ligature in which the second τ resembles γ (e.g., BSB gr. 134, line 7; M, line 14, though again, in M this looks more like a 'V').

In light of all these palaeographical observations, it is worth considering each of the three manuscripts that share *M*'s *minuscula bouletée* in turn for what they can tell us about the cultural context of *M* and its alchemical epigram. BSB gr. 134 is a highly luxurious manuscript and, as mentioned above, is the earliest extant copy of the compilation on horse medicine known as the *Hippiatrika*. Like *M*, then, it is a middle Byzantine technical compilation drawing on a range of older and more recent material.⁶⁷ It is often said to have been produced for Emperor Constantine VII Porphyrogenitus. While this may be a plausible inference, it should be noted that the evidence is palaeographical and stylistic; there is no explicit ascription in the manuscript as it survives today, so at least in theory it could have been produced for another wealthy patron.⁶⁸ Still, it is undeniably an extremely fine product crafted with the highest-quality parchment, layout, ornament and script available in tenth-century Constantinople. Only the very wealthiest individuals could have afforded to commission such a manuscript.

BAV Barb. gr. 310 is likewise a luxury object. It is also a compilation, in this case of poetry. A small-format codex gathering Anacreontic poetry and alphabet acrostics in stress-based verse dating from the sixth to the early tenth century, this manuscript has been dated to either the first or last quarter of the tenth century.⁶⁹ Either way, it is another very fine, very expensive book produced in the capital for a wealthy patron.

67. BSB gr. 134 contains the 'B recension' of the *Hippiatrika*, which is neatly organised according to headings. The 'M recension' of the *Hippiatrika* (extant in a manuscript from the 10th or 11th century, BnF MS gr. 2322; diktyon 51953) is, by contrast, structured as a loose series of texts and excerpts with topical clusters but no sharply defined overarching scheme, leading me to conclude that it was, among well-known middle Byzantine compilations, most similar in structure to the alchemical codex *M*; see Roberts (as in n. 4), p. 101. On these recensions of the *Hippiatrika*, see McCabe (as in n. 51), pp. 18–27.

68. L. Cohn, 'Bemerkungen zu den Konstantinischen Sammelwerken', *Byzantinische Zeitschrift*, IX, 1900, pp. 158–60, who was concerned to show that the traditional ascription of the *Hippiatrika* to Constantine VII was correct with respect to the collection as a whole (in contrast to the earlier authors named in the collection), pointed to two pieces of evidence to support his claim: first, that the compilation was of a kind with other compilations ascribed to Constantine VII, in particular the *Geoponika*; and second, that the oldest manuscript, BSB gr. 134, was very fine and 'gives the distinct impression' that it was produced for the emperor ('Die Handschrift macht ganz den Eindruck, als ob sie das für den Kaiser bestimmte Exemplar der *Hippiatrika* bildete und in kaiserlichem Besitze war'; p. 159). In light of its 10th-century date, he reasoned, it was quite likely that Constantine VII was the emperor for whom it was produced, and that an original dedication saying so had since been lost. Accordingly, he suggested that BSB gr. 134 was to be

identified with a *Hippiatrika* manuscript listed in a catalogue of books owned by Michael Cantacuzenus (d. 1578) with the note that it was dedicated to Constantine VII (*De antiquitatibus et libris manuscriptis Constantinopolitanis commentatio*, ed. R. Foerster, Rostock 1877, p. 27; for the date of the catalogue and the death of Michael Cantacuzenus at the hands of the Ottoman Sultan Murad III, see *ibid.*, pp. 6–7). K. Weitzmann, *Die byzantinische Buchmalerei des 9. und 10. Jahrhunderts*, I, Berlin 1935, p. 17, considered it the 10th-century product of the imperial scriptorium, based on the style of its decoration. See also J. Irigoin, 'Pour une étude des centres de copie byzantins (suite)', *Scriptorium*, XIII, 1959, pp. 177–209 (180–81); cited by S. Lazaris, *Art et science vétérinaire à Byzance*, Turnhout 2010, p. 133. It is standard in the literature on Greek palaeography to say that it was 'dedicated to' or 'written for' Constantine VII with no further comment or qualification; e.g., Agati, *La minuscola 'bouletée'* (as in n. 50), I, p. 212; Pérez Martín, 'The Reception of Xenophon' (as in n. 51), p. 831 n. 56.

69. Lauxtermann (as in n. 33), I, p. 123. See also Gallavotti (as in n. 51). Many of its folios have been lost, but its table of contents permits a reconstruction of the original contents, much as in the case of *M*. Agati, 'Su due manoscritti' (as in n. 51), p. 625, dated the script to late in the second half of the 10th century, because she considered it to be the more mature work of the same scribe who produced BSB gr. fol. 73 (p. 619); she is followed by Gallavotti (as in n. 51), p. 31 n. 6; Cavallo (as in n. 51), p. 18 n. 32; and Lauxtermann (as in n. 33), I, p. 123 n. 133. By contrast, Pérez Martín,

BSB gr. fol. 73 is a somewhat different sort of manuscript. Rather than a collection of older and more recent texts like the other two, it gathers fourteen orations by Gregory of Nazianzus,⁷⁰ who was a favourite author among middle Byzantine readers.⁷¹ Its 227 folios were cut from good parchment but not the very finest.⁷² Still, it was laid out carefully and with plenty of empty space on the page, like the other two manuscripts.⁷³ In short, it was far from a cheap product, but it was also not up to the level of luxury found in the other two.

The palaeographical affinity of the alchemical epigram to these three manuscripts brings us closer to the context of M's production and use. Based on the comparative analysis presented above, it seems quite likely that the same scribe or scriptorium produced all four manuscripts, and that M was produced sometime in the second half of the tenth century. M is not a luxury manuscript of the highest quality like BAV Barb. gr. 310 and BSB gr. 134, so it need not have been produced for an emperor:⁷⁴ apart from embellishments to the script and ornament on its opening quire, including the alchemical epigram, and the first page of the first text of the corpus (Fig. 3), it was executed with care but in a considerably less costly way, with limited ornamentation and, as we have seen, a plainer minuscule script. This suggests that the manuscript was more like BSB gr. fol. 73, or perhaps even humbler, intended for a wealthy patron who wished to use and study it, someone with means but not unlimited means.

4. Literary context

The most obvious place to look for the literary context of a dedicatory ἐπίγραμμα ('inscription') is the book in which it is placed,⁷⁵ and, indeed, this epigram's conception of alchemy is clearly based on familiarity with the alchemical corpus. It should also be read against the broader background of philosophical discourse current among Byzantine intellectuals. 'Nature vanquishing natures' (φύσιν / ... φύσεις νικῶσαν', lines 9–10), for example, is a recurring Pseudo-Democritan formula.⁷⁶ The poem's language also plays on alchemical terminology. For example, in lines 14–19, 'When you discover this nature ...', the epigram evokes the moment when the reader will discover the mystery the book promises. The reader is invited to marvel at the inspired men who imitated God, taking on the role of demiurge (δημιουργῶν, line 16).⁷⁷ Here the epigram plays on the standard meaning of 'bodies

'The Reception of Xenophon' (as in n. 51), pp. 830–31, described it as having been produced not long after 920.

70. Agati, 'Su due manoscritti' (as in n. 51), p. 619.

71. S. Papaioannou, *Michael Psellos: Rhetoric and Authorship in Byzantium*, Cambridge 2013, pp. 56–63.

72. Agati, 'Su due manoscritti' (as in n. 51), p. 619: 'discretta qualità'. Cf. Berger (as in n. 56), p. 5: 'Feines Pergament'.

73. Agati, 'Su due manoscritti' (as in n. 51), p. 619.

74. For that matter, perhaps we should pause before automatically assigning even the finest manuscripts to

the imperial library based solely on their finery. The 14th-century copy of Xenophon in Paris, BnF MS gr. 1640 (diktyon 51263), descends from a manuscript, presumably a lavish one, that was given as a gift to Emperor Leo VI (r. 886–912); see Lauxtermann (as in n. 33), I, pp. 208–09. This should remind us that courtiers other than the emperor had the means to produce books that were lavish enough for the imperial library; at least in theory, then, these same wealthy individuals could have produced such codices for each other or themselves as well.

75. See below, n. 114.

76. Berthelot, in *CAAG*, III, p. 3 n. 1.

and spirits' (σωμάτων καὶ πνευμάτων) which these godly men 'create', and on the special alchemical sense of this phrase: 'bodies' are metals, and 'spirits' are vapours of various sorts.⁷⁸ These men attained to great wisdom, for they learned to provide bodies with a soul (ψυχοῦν), and to take away and give back life (line 18). Endowing a body with a soul is, of course, the role of the Creator (δημιουργός). Philo of Alexandria writes that by means of the senses, 'the demiurge endowed the [human] body with a soul'.⁷⁹ To endow with a soul was also seen as a technical skill. A Hellenistic epigram preserved and read in middle Byzantium begins: 'Who endowed stone with a soul?', referring to a marble statue of Aphrodite in Cnidus that was so lifelike that Praxiteles the sculptor must have made it, or perhaps the goddess herself had descended to Cnidus.⁸⁰ To 'kill and to give life again' (ἀποκτείνειν τε καὶ ζωοῦν πάλιν; line 18), in alchemical terminology, could mean to effect the dissolution of a metal and then its regeneration.⁸¹ The effect of this semi-divine artistry is to endow things with unexpected shapes and forms (line 19). Thus, the epigram, participating in a long Greek literary tradition of comparing skilful craftsmanship to divine demiurgy, presents alchemy not only as a technical craft with its own terminology, but also a divine one tasked with nothing less than the act of creation.

Echoes of alchemical texts include plays on words that are not obviously alchemical. It is at least possible that the riddle in line 14, 'let me not say who [this nature] is' (μὴ γὰρ ὅστις ἢ φράσω) refers to Christ in a way meant to parallel the opening prayer of Stephen of Alexandria's fourth lecture, one of the texts in the compilation.⁸² The word εὐοπτία ('splendour', or 'beautiful appearance': εὐοπτία, line 6) appears several times in the Greek alchemical corpus contained in M, but is otherwise quite rare.⁸³ It might also have called to mind, however faintly, a late

77. In patristic literature, this usually refers to God's role as creator of the universe: *A Patristic Greek Lexicon*, ed. G. W. H. Lampe, Oxford 1961, s.vv. δημιουργός A.2.a-j, δημιουργέω 3.a-h. As Lampe notes at s.v. δημιουργέω 3.1, Theodoret of Cyrrhus (d. 458) argues (*Questions about Genesis*, question 20, *Patrologia Graeca*, LXXX, col. 105B-C) that human beings can imitate God's demiurgy (e.g., by building a house) but can only apply themselves to pre-existing matter rather than creating the matter itself (they also need time, effort, tools, the products of other craftsmen, and so on, unlike God). In the epigram, there seems to be intentional ambiguity as to whether the *andres demiourgoi* in question are remaining within this limit or, by acting as 'demiurges of bodies', transgressing it.

78. See *CAAG*, III, p. 4 n. 2, commenting on this passage: 'Le mot *corps*, σώματα, s'applique dans la langue des alchimistes, aux métaux régénérés de leurs oxydes et autres minerais. Le mot *esprit*, πνεύματα, a un sens plus vague; il signifie spécialement les substances volatiles que l'on peut fixer sur les métaux, ou en séparer.'

79. Philo of Alexandria, *De opificio mundi*, ed. L. Cohn et al., I, Berlin 1896, p. 48, line 16 (§48): 'τῶν αἰσθήσεων ... αἷ τὸ μὲν σῶμα ἐψύχωσεν ὁ δημιουργός'. Cf. Basil, *Hexaemeron*, VIII.1, ed. E. Amand de

Mendieta and S. Y. Rudberg, Berlin 1997, p. 127, line 19.

80. This epigram is known to us from the anthology of Maximus Planudes (d. c. 1305): *Anthologia Planudea*, 4.159, 'τίς λίθον ἐψύχωσε' = 'Greek Anthology', xvi, no. 159; *Anthologia Graeca*, ed. and tr. H. Beckby, 4 vols, Munich 1957, IV, p. 388.

81. Cf. *CAAG*, III, p. 4 n. 3, commenting on this passage: 'Ces expressions mystiques signifient la production des métaux, leur disparition par oxydation, dissolution, etc., et leur régénération.'

82. As suggested to me by an anonymous reviewer for this *Journal*. See Stephen, *Lectures*, 4, ed. Papatthanassiou (as in n. 4), p. 173, lines 1–16 = *Physici et medici graeci minores*, ed. J. L. Ideler, 2 vols, Leipzig 1841–42, II, p. 213, lines 9–27 = M, fols 16^v, line 13, to 17^r, line 2. Stephen's prayer uses standard descriptions of Christ to emphasise his role as God's wisdom and giver of knowledge.

83. It is absent from LSJ; and from Lampe (as in n. 77). In E. Trapp, *Lexikon zur byzantinischen Gräzität, besonders des 9.–12. Jahrhunderts*, Vienna 1994, s.v. εὐοπτία, it is defined as 'gutes Aussehen, schöne Erscheinung'. The attestations listed are all from the Greek alchemical corpus: Stephen of Alexandria, *Lectures*, 2, line 154, and 6, line 234 (ed.

antique legend about a Delphic priestess named Euoptia,⁸⁴ which was adapted by John of Damascus (d. 749 or c. 753–54), or a later interpolator, in his *Discourse on the Holy Nativity of Christ*, where Euoptia now announces Christ's coming.⁸⁵ Given the medieval popularity of pagan oracles predicting Christ's coming and the wide circulation of John of Damascus's *Discourse*,⁸⁶ perhaps the word could have reminded a Byzantine reader of Euoptia's Christian oracular profile.⁸⁷

Finally, several phrases in the epigram echo verses in the late antique iambic poems attributed to Heliodorus, Theophrastus, Hierotheus and Archelaus which figure prominently in M's collection,⁸⁸ particularly that of Archelaus. At one point Archelaus speaks of a latent 'blackening' ('μέλανσιν') that lies 'within, hidden as it were' ('ἔνδον ὡς κεκρυμμένην'),⁸⁹ which could have partially inspired the alchemical epigram's first line. Further along, Archelaus speaks of 'a bright glance' ('φαιδρῶ βλέμματι'),⁹⁰ much as the epigram speaks of 'the mind's bright eye' ('νοῦς τὸ φαιδρὸν ὄμμα', line 5). Further parallels for both of these lines will be examined below. Another echo of Archelaus might be discerned in line 18 of the alchemical epigram, the structure of which seems to reflect a pattern favoured by Archelaus.⁹¹

The language of the epigram can also be situated in the broader philosophical, often Neoplatonic, language current among elite Byzantines, which they employed

Papathanassiou, as in n. 4, pp. 166 and 197 = ed. Ideler, as in n. 82, II, pp. 207, line 16, and 230, line 31) = M, fols 13^r, line 15, and 28^v, line 16; and the alchemical poems of Hierotheus, line 91, and Archelaus, line 167 (edited as carmina III and IV by Goldschmidt, as in n. 29) = M, fols 54^v, line 12, and 59^v, line 29. Trapp also refers to H. Estienne, *Thesaurus Graecae linguae*, 8 vols, Paris 1831–65, III, col. 2372, where the sole citation is this very passage from the alchemical epigram, as edited in Bernard's appendix to Palladius (as in n. 18).

84. Recounted in the *Account of Events in Persia* (Εξήγησις τῶν πραγμάτων ἐν Περσίῳ) ascribed to Athanasius, Patriarch of Antioch (d. 599), ed. E. Bratke in *Das sogenannte Religionsgespräch am Hof der Sasaniden*, Leipzig 1899, pp. 1–45 (6, line 7); cited in John of Damascus, *Die Schriften ...*, ed. B. Kotter, 7 vols, Berlin 1969–2013, v, p. 311 n. 14.

85. John of Damascus, ed. Kotter (as in n. 84), v, pp. 324–47 (333 = §7, line 14: 'Ἰωάννου, τοῦ ταπεινοῦ καὶ ἐλαχίστου μοναχοῦ τοῦ Δαμασκηνοῦ, λόγος εἰς τὴν ἁγίαν Χριστοῦ γέννησιν'); cited by the *TLG* (lemma search for εὐοπτία, 4 Nov. 2016); this (along with its source, see n. 84) is the only occurrence of the word cited by the *TLG* that is not in M. This homily is attributed to John of Damascus in 48 out of 58 manuscripts that contain the beginning of the text; on its authenticity see Kotter, *ibid.*, pp. 307–10. V. Kontouma, *John of Damascus: New Studies on His Life and Works*, Farnham 2015, art. I, pp. 1–43 (42 and n. 219), following Kotter, considers that the text as a whole is authentic but that the oracle narrative being discussed here (§7–10) is a later interpolation.

86. It survives at least in part in at least 72 manuscripts, of which several date to the 11th century (Kotter's nos 65 [11th or 12th century], 152 [fragment], 181, 197, 296, 350 [11th or 12th century]) and one to the 10th (Kotter's no. 381); see Kotter (as in n. 84), pp. 313–15, along with 3–55.

87. Lines 5–6 of the epigram might even have been read as a *double-entendre*. Beautiful things (such as lustrous metals) may well elevate one's thoughts (a Platonic commonplace, as in the *Phaedrus*), but so too may all-wise Euoptias, that is, 'well-seeing' prophetesses, if read as an allusion to this particular prophetess, with the ability to see and the inspiration to reveal the future incarnation of the one true God. Bratke, in his edition of the homily's source (as in n. 84), p. 146 n. 1, notes that Euoptia is aptly named.

88. For the dating of these poems see Lauxtermann (as in n. 33), II, pp. 205–07, who places them in the 5th or early 6th century, based on the frequencies of oxytone and proparoxytone line endings and despite their strict adherence to 12 syllables, which he notes is attested already in late antiquity and possibly even earlier. For the previous 8th-century dating see above, n. 29.

89. Ed. Goldschmidt (as in n. 29), p. 54, line 163 = M, fol. 59^v, line 25. In M, this line is distinguished by a rough marginal mark.

90. Ed. Goldschmidt (as in n. 29), p. 56, line 211 = M, fol. 60^r, line 15.

91. E.g., ed. Goldschmidt (as in n. 29), p. 54, line 155, 'κρατουμένη τε καὶ φιλουμένη πάλιν', and p. 55, line 173, 'τεχνουργικῶς λειῶν τε καὶ πλύνων πάλιν' = M, fol. 59^v, line 17, and fol. 60^r, line 6. The second of these lines in M is marked in the margin.

not only in alchemy but also in theology, physics and other fields. The phrase translated here as ‘in a god-inspired way’ (‘ἐνθέω τρόπῳ’, line 10) has several resonances. Being ‘inspired’ (ἐνθεος) is associated with divination in Plato’s *Phaedrus* and *Timaeus*, and the term is used by Neoplatonists such as Julian, Iamblichus and the Christian Origen, often adverbially (ἐνθέως).⁹² The particular phrase that we find in the epigram, on the other hand, seems to be relatively rare. It occurs in a hymn to St Gregory of Nazianzus, under the heading ‘On the golden icon’ (‘Τῇ εἰκόνι τῆ χρυσοῦ’).⁹³ Here, it has a similar theme of knowledge revealed: ‘Already having purified yourself by the knowing Logos and the inspired manner (ἐνθέω... τρόπῳ) of your virtues, and having instructed [or: transformed] your mind by divine things, you were intellectually initiated into the ineffable [secrets] of Christ, anointed high priest, and proclaimed a shepherd, O most excellent theologian.’⁹⁴ In the eleventh century, Psellus took this image of Gregory of Nazianzus’s inspiration a step further, conceiving of Gregory’s words as the product not simply of divine inspiration but of his own autonomous act of creation, demiurgy, an act which Psellus describes as being ‘beyond nature’ (‘ὑπὲρ τὴν φύσιν’) and which he compares to God’s own radically original act of creation.⁹⁵ These notions are not far from the epigram’s ‘nature / which alone vanquishes natures in a god-inspired way’ (‘φύσιν, / μόνην φύσεις νικῶσαν, ἐνθέω τρόπῳ’, lines 9–10) and the alchemist as demiurge.

When the epigram turns to Theodore, it describes him as having learned the transformations of a special kind of matter (lines 20–21). The term ἔκβασις (line 21), literally, the act of ‘going out’, can also mean ‘change’ or ‘transformation’ (μετάβασις), as Aristotle and others use it. The Stoics Zeno (fourth/third century BC) and Chrysippus (third century BC) use it to refer to the fulfilment of a prediction by divination, while Neoplatonic philosophers such as Porphyry (third century AD) and Damascius (d. after AD 538) use it to refer to space-extension’s ‘departure from itself’ and the intellect’s ‘departure’ (in the sense of ‘distinction’) from being.⁹⁶ A slightly different sense of ἔκβασις that might also fit the context, if more loosely, is ‘outcome’ or ‘result’; perhaps we are meant to view the special kind of matter as the cause of a range of ‘outcomes’, that is, the changes it effects in ordinary matter.⁹⁷

92. Plato: LSJ, s.v. ἐνθεος. Julian and the others: Lampe (as in n. 78), s.v. ἐνθέως.

93. *Analecta hymnica graeca e codicibus eruta Italiae inferioris*, ed. G. Schirò, 13 vols, Rome 1966–1983, v, p. 355, line 23 = 25 January, canon 30.1, line 312 (ode 7).

94. *Ibid.*, lines 24–32: ‘Προκαθάρας ἑαυτὸν / τῷ ἐπιστήμονι λόγῳ / καὶ τῷ ἐνθέῳ τῶν ἀρετῶν σου τρόπῳ / καὶ στοιχειώσας τὸν νοῦν τοῖς θείοις, / ἐμυήθης λογικῶς / τὰ ἀπόρρητα Χριστοῦ, / ἐχρίσθης ἱεράρχης / καὶ ἀνεδείχθης ποιμῆν, / κράτιστε θεολόγε.’

95. For this reading of Psellus see Papaioannou (as in n. 71), pp. 74–78, where ‘autonomy’ is central to the argument.

96. For all of these definitions, see LSJ (as in n. 83), s.v. ἔκβασις, which notes that Porphyry and

Damascius use it in the sense of ‘emanation’ or ‘procession’. To be more precise, Porphyry speaks of physical bulk or volume (ὄγκος) as an ‘ἐκβασις... ἄφ’ ἑαυτοῦ... καὶ κατακερματισμὸς τῆς δυνάμεως’: Porphyry, *Sententiae*, 35, lines 1–4; ed. L. Brisson, 2 vols, Paris 2005, I, p. 350. Damascius describes the intellect as gaining awareness of a distinction between itself and being, even as being remains indistinct (Ὁ γὰρ νοῦς ἑαυτὸν διακεκριμένον ἄπ’ ἐκείνου ἰδὼν, ἐκεῖνο δὲ ἀδιάκριτον μείναν) whereupon the intellect ‘τὴν ἄπ’ ἐκείνου [i.e., being] ἔκβασις διακρίσιν ὠνόμασεν’: Damascius, *Traité des premiers principes*, II, *De la triade et de l’unifié*, ed. L. G. Westerink, tr. J. Combès, Paris 1989, p. 153 = idem, *Dubitationes et solutiones de primis principiis*, in *Platonis Parmenidem*, ed. C.-É. Ruelle, 2 vols, Paris 1889, I, pp. 183–84.

In the context, it is certainly natural to read the term ἔκβασις as referring to the changes which matter can undergo, since the book that Theodore has compiled revolves around ways of manipulating matter. Another layer of meaning is, however, suggested by the use of the word in several late antique Christian works. Clement of Alexandria (c. 150–before 215) writes that ‘baptism ... is stepping out (ἔκβασις) of matter’.⁹⁸ Gregory of Nazianzus speaks of virginity as an ‘escape’ (ἔκβασις) from the body.⁹⁹ Reading line 21 of the epigram in light of these passages, we might understand its meaning rather differently: ‘Discerning and learning the ways to step out’ of matter. In this reading, ἔκβασις is not a process which matter undergoes (transformation) but rather a movement away from matter.¹⁰⁰ That these ways to ‘step out’ of matter should be ‘hidden ... within’, that is, within matter, would surely be a paradoxical, ‘enigmatic’ proposition, consonant with the epigram’s sentiment (αἰνιγματωδῶς ἔνδον ἐγκεκρυμμένης, line 22). Perhaps the line should be read both ways at once: the transformation of matter is itself the means to depart from matter; and it is a process localised within matter itself. To escape matter, one must transform it.

Much of the language in the epigram is standard Byzantine literary Greek. Some of it follows on centuries of use, like the epithet ‘gold-rich’ (line 3), a long-lived literary commonplace. Homer had used it to glorify Mycenae,¹⁰¹ and it was still current in the Middle Ages.¹⁰² As a description of ‘veins’ it is, to my knowledge, unique to the alchemical epigram.¹⁰³ A possible parallel for associating this particular epithet with veins of gold within the earth rather than simply wealth, though certainly not a source for the alchemical epigram’s usage, is found in the

97. Lampe (as in n. 77), s.v. ἔκβασις 2. See n. 126 below.

98. Clement of Alexandria, *Eclogae ex scripturis prophetiis*, ed. O. Stählin, Leipzig 1909, p. 138, line 16 = *Patrologia Graeca*, IX, cols 700D–701A (cited by Lampe, as in n. 77, s.v. ἔκβασις): ‘τὸ βάπτισμα ... τῆς ὕλης ἐστὶν ἔκβασις’. One is thus illuminated by immaterial light: ‘Leading us out of disorder, the Lord illuminates us, bringing us to the shadowless light which is no longer material’ (‘ἐξάγων οὖν τῆς ἀταξίας ἡμᾶς ὁ κύριος φωτίζει, εἰς τὸ φῶς ἄγων τὸ ἄσκιον καὶ οὐκέτι ὑλικόν’, col. 701A, lines 3–5).

99. See the passage cited by Lampe (as in n. 77), s.v. ἔκβασις.

100. For this use of ἔκβασις with the genitive see LSJ, s.v. ἐκβαίνω A.I.1, and Clement’s line quoted above, n. 98.

101. Homer, *Iliad*, XI.46. Other authors used it to glorify Olympus, Delphi and Aphrodite; see LSJ, s.v. πολύχρυσος.

102. In his *Encomium* to Emperor John II Comnenus (r. 1118–43), celebrating the Cilician and Syrian campaign of 1137–38, Nicephorus Basilaca declares that the city of Bizā’a (Πιζᾶ, northeast of Aleppo), conquered and sacked by the emperor, was richer in gold than gold-rich Mycenae: *Gli encomi per l’imperatore e per il patriarca*, ed. R. Maisano, Naples 1977, p. 111

(§27, lines 635–36) = Nicephorus Basilaca, *Orationes et epistolae*, ed. A. Garzya, Leipzig 1984, p. 65, line 2, ‘ὕπερ τὰς πολυχρύσους Μυκίνας ἢ πόλις πολύχρυσος’. For the context of this campaign see Maisano, pp. 19, 210–11. The passage also alludes to Pindar: ‘ὡς ἀπὸ “ξανθῶν νεφελῶν” [Olympians, 7.49] ὁ χρυσοῦς ἐμμεκάετο’; lines 640–41, ed. Maisano, p. 111 = Garzya, p. 65, lines 5–6. (By coincidence, this phrase too might have carried chemical connotations, at least for some readers: the sublimated vapours used to produce, or imitate, gold.)

103. I thank an anonymous reviewer for this *Journal* for drawing my attention to an analogous phrase in a book epigram on the *Onomasticon* of Julius Pollux (2nd century): ‘πολυχρόνουσ [or: πολυκρόνουσ] φλέβας’. The *Onomasticon* of Julius Pollux is contained in a number of manuscripts; see *Epigrammatum Anthologia Palatina, cum Planudeis et appendice nova epigrammatum veterum ex libris et marmoribus ductorum*, ed. E. Cougny, 3 vols, Paris 1864, III, pp. 327–28 = appendix, *Epigrammata demonstrativa*, no. 222, line 5. The five manuscripts listed as containing this epigram in the DBBE, type 2510, date to the 14th or 15th centuries, though the epigram itself may have been composed earlier. The similarity of phrasing, combined with its rarity, suggests that one epigrammatist may have intentionally used the other; but without a date for the Pollux epigram, it is difficult to say who influenced whom.

commentary to Plato's *First Alcibiades* by the Neoplatonist Olympiodorus (sixth century), where Olympiodorus marshals Homer's description of 'gold-rich Mycenae' as proof of Sparta's wealth. The Spartans really were rich, as Socrates says, Olympiodorus insists. One of his four pieces of evidence is testimony that Sparta possesses veins of gold and silver; it is as his next piece of evidence that he cites the phrase from Homer.¹⁰⁴ Juxtaposed like this, the two pieces of evidence suggest that Olympiodorus is partly explaining the Homeric phrase as a reference to gold mines. There is no indication that the alchemical epigram is referring to this passage of Olympiodorus; but nonetheless it does show that the epithet could occasionally be associated with gold that was yet to be unearthed, as in the epigram.

The epithet *παγγέραστος* (line 23), 'renowned by all', used to describe Theodore's mind, is an example of more recent vocabulary. This word had evolved primarily in a Christian context and appears to have been uncommon before the eighth century.¹⁰⁵ It is slightly better attested for the middle Byzantine period.¹⁰⁶ George the Monk (ninth century) used it in three different places: to describe Abraham when he had become famous for teaching astronomy in Egypt, to describe Emperor Titus (r. 79–81) after he piously conquered Jerusalem, and to describe the land of Jerusalem itself.¹⁰⁷ In the tenth century, it was applied to the day of resurrection,¹⁰⁸ and in the eleventh, to St Athanasius the Athonite.¹⁰⁹

We may note further that the commonplace image of raising the mind's eye to contemplate higher things is executed here (lines 5–6) with words that recall a

104. Olympiodorus, *Commentary on the First Alcibiades of Plato*, ed. L. G. Westerink, 2nd edn, Amsterdam 1982, p. 103 (162.6–10): 'καὶ τῷ ἑτεροκινήτῳ δὲ πλούτῳ ὑπερεῖχον, εἶγε λέγεται περὶ αὐτῶν ὅτι δύο μοίρας τῶν προσόδων ἀπῆτουν τοὺς ὑπηκόους, καὶ ὅτι λέγονται εἶναι φλέβες ἀργυρίτιδες καὶ χρυσίτιδες: καὶ τὸ "πολυχρῦσοιο Μυκίτης"· καὶ ὅτι λέγεται περὶ αὐτῶν ὅτι εἰσὶν τὸ χρυσίον παρ' αὐτοῖς οὐκ ἔτι ἐξήλει.'

105. There is no entry for it in LSJ; nor is one given by Trapp (as in n. 83). But see Lampe (as in n. 77), s.v. *παγγέραστος*, citing two examples: Nectarius (4th-century archbishop of Constantinople), who uses it to address a saint (*Patrologia Graeca*, LXXXIX, col. 1840A); and George of Pisidia, who applies it to the seven Maccabee martyrs for their loyalty to Mosaic law (L. Sternbach, 'Georgii Pisidae carmina inedita. Pars II', *Wiener Studien*, xiv, 1892, pp. 51–68 [51, poem no. 21]: 'Ἡ παγγέραστος ἐβδομάς τῶν μαρτύρων / νόμῳ θανοῦσα τὴν χάριν συνεισφέρει').

106. A lemma search for *παγγέραστος* in the *TLG* (14 Mar. 2020) yielded 14 results of which one is the alchemical epigram and another an undated hymn. Of the remaining 12, the earliest are the 8th-/9th-century *translatio* of St Euphemia of Chalcedon by Constantine of Tius (*BHG*, no. 621), ed. F. Halkin in *Euphémie de Chalcedoine: Légendes byzantines*, Brussels 1965, p. 105 (§17, line 10), where it appears as one in a long list of epithets praising the saint, and three instances in the chronicle of George the Monk. Three more of the results are duplicates: they are the same

three passages in a shorter recension of George the Monk's chronicle. Two further results are also duplicates: passages from the chronicle of George Cedrenus drawn from George the Monk. That leaves the two hagiographical passages discussed in what follows, along with a line from George Metochites (13th century). Because the *TLG* is currently spottier in its coverage of later texts, the word might have been more common in the middle Byzantine period than these results would seem to indicate. A poem in Venice, Biblioteca Nazionale Marciana MS gr. 134 (12th century, diktyon 69605; edition DBBE, occurrence 22114), fols 191^r–193^v, line 26, applies it to the afterlife; and a rhyming poem in Paris, BnF MS gr. 12 (AD 1419; diktyon 49572; edition DBBE, occurrence 24516), fol. B^f, applies it to the diadem of King David (στέμμα, line 2 of the poem) that pales, like his other royal trappings, by comparison with the Psalter that he composed.

107. George the Monk, *Chronicon*, ed. C. de Boor, 2 vols, Leipzig 1904, I, p. 96, line 1, and II, pp. 437, line 23, and 715, lines 20–21.

109. *Vita Euthymii patriarchae Constantinopolitani* (*BHG*, no. 651), ed. and tr. (French) P. Karlin-Hayter, Brussels 1970, p. 63, line 35 (§10).

109. Athanasius the Monk, *Vita Athanasii Athonitae* (*BHG*, no. 187), §52, line 14, in *Vitae duae antiquae Sancti Athanasii Athonitae*, ed. J. Noret, Turnhout 1982, p. 26.

line from Gregory of Nazianzus's famous funeral oration for Basil of Caesarea,¹¹⁰ which was a popular rhetorical model much studied by learned readers in the Byzantine Empire, even those whose native language was not Greek.¹¹¹ The word μουσοστόλος (line 12), 'Muse-decorated', on the other hand, may be unique to this epigram.¹¹²

5. Dedicatory book epigrams

If we compare the alchemical epigram to other dedicatory book epigrams in middle Byzantine manuscripts, especially of the tenth century, we find that it fits squarely and comfortably within this genre.¹¹³ The typical dedicatory epigram for a patron celebrates the texts contained in the manuscript, or past sages who authored them or imparted their wisdom, and praises the renowned intelligence and solicitude of the distinguished patron who had the manuscript produced.¹¹⁴ Especially in epigrams composed before c. 1000, the generosity of patrons with their money is typically alluded to only obliquely—as in the alchemical epigram, with its subtle hint at Theodore's wealth and loyalty.¹¹⁵

It is instructive to compare the alchemical epigram to a sample of tenth-century dedicatory epigrams with an eye to their shared themes, choice of vocabulary and verbal structure.¹¹⁶ The 'Leo Bible' (BAV MS Reg. gr. 1, tenth century) bears, on its first folio, a dedicatory epigram of sixty dodecasyllable lines.¹¹⁷ Christ is called 'Ruler of All' in the first line of this epigram and again further on,¹¹⁸ just as in the last line of the alchemical epigram. The Bible, the book the epigram introduces, is 'all-wise' in the way it teaches us,¹¹⁹ just as the alchemical epigram directs the reader to turn his attention to the 'all-wise splendours' (line 6) to be found in the book before him, which it also describes as 'this book of all-wise thoughts' (line 27). Both epigrams celebrate discovery: the one in the Leo Bible recounts that

110. I owe this observation to an anonymous reviewer for this *Journal*. See Gregory of Nazianzus, *Oration* 43, §41, lines 8–9, in his *Discours 42–43*, ed. and tr. J. Bernardi, Paris 1992, p. 214 = *Patrologia Graeca*, xxxvi, col. 552A: 'ἀλλ' ὑψοῦ τὴν κεφαλὴν διάρας καὶ κύκλω τὸ τῆς ψυχῆς ὄμμα περιαγαγόν'.

111. A. M. Roberts, *Reason and Revelation in Byzantine Antioch: The Christian Translation Program of Abdallah ibn al-Fadl*, Oakland CA 2020, p. 157 and n. 25.

112. I thank one of the anonymous reviewers for pointing out this possibility. The alchemical epigram is the only example cited by Trapp (as in n. 83). The word does not appear in LSJ; Lampe (as in n. 77); or F. Montanari, *The Brill Dictionary of Ancient Greek*, Leiden 2015 (cf. s.v. μουσοπόλος, 'Muse-serving').

113. Following the lead of Byzantine sources, Lauxtermann (as in n. 33), I, pp. 26–34, has sensibly proposed defining Byzantine epigrams without reference to ancient or modern criteria (in which an epigram tends to be a short poem with a witty ending), but rather as verses that were inscribed (or imitated those that were inscribed), whether on stone or in a

manuscript as an introduction to, comment on or dedication (e.g., to a patron) of the manuscript's contents.

114. For many such examples see *ibid.*, I, pp. 206–12; and DBBE.

115. For the prevalence of this kind of reference before c. 1000 see *ibid.*, pp. 34–45, esp. 35. For the reference to Theodore's wealth in the epigram see n. 21 above.

116. For my discussion of the following book epigrams, I draw on the DBBE and the bibliographical references it cites for each epigram.

117. Diktyon 66171. See *La Bible du patrice Léon: Codex Reginensis Graecus 1. Commentaire codicologique, paléographique, philologique et artistique*, ed. P. Canart, Vatican City 2011; and for the dedicatory epigram, 'The Epigrams', ed. and tr. C. Mango, *ibid.*, pp. 59–79 (59–64).

118. Leo Bible, dedicatory epigram (as in n. 117), line 1, 'τοῦ παντάνακτος καὶ θεοῦ λόγου φύσει'; line 10, 'δι' ὧν προῆλθε παντάναξ θε(ε)ῶς λόγος'.

119. *Ibid.*, line 9: 'ἡ βιβλος ἡμᾶς ἐκδιδάσκει πανσόφως'.

‘Solomon found the breadth of wisdom’;¹²⁰ the reader of M will ‘find a wealth of higher knowledge’ (line 8), for ‘lovers of divine knowledge alone have found’ (line 13) the wondrous ‘nature’ that can be used to make anything. Both books contain wisdom: in one can be found ‘the wise, god-inspired / Evangelists’,¹²¹ in the other ‘the wisest writing’ (line 7). In the Leo Bible epigram, St Paul’s mouth is ‘ἐνθεον’, ‘god-inspired’;¹²² the alchemical epigram uses this word three times, describing the inspired way in which the one wondrous nature conquers other natures (line 10),¹²³ the brilliant men who discovered that nature (line 15), and the qualities of the book’s patron, Theodore (line 24). Both epigrams speak metaphorically of ‘being rich’.¹²⁴ The patron of each epigram is a ‘loyal’ (‘πιστός’) servant of the emperor.¹²⁵ The word ἐκβάσεις, discussed above, appears in the Leo Bible epigram as well, also in the plural, there meaning ‘outcome’.¹⁶ Just as the brilliant chemists of old acted as demiurges (‘ὡς δημιουργῶν’, line 16), in the Leo Bible epigram God’s Logos acts as demiurge of sky and earth.¹²⁷ Finally, in the Leo Bible epigram Christ’s taking on human nature is ‘ξένην’, ‘strange’ or ‘astonishing’,¹²⁸ a word that appears three times in the alchemical epigram: twice in line 19 (‘ξένως’), to describe the demiurgical fashioning and moulding of matter, and once in line 26, to describe the alchemical corpus which Theodore has compiled.

Already in late antiquity, ξένος was sometimes used, as here, to describe an object of wonder; it became something of a stock phrase for poets who wished to emphasise how remarkable their subjects were, especially for middle Byzantine dodecasyllablists looking for a moveable paroxytone word with which to end a line.¹²⁹ In both the Leo Bible epigram and the alchemical epigram, the ‘strange’ or ‘remarkable’ thing has to do with changing matter: the Incarnation of Christ and chemical transformation respectively. This may indicate a tendency to describe material transformation as ‘strange’; a didactic poem on the Eucharistic liturgy ascribed in later manuscripts to Psellus does something similar.¹³⁰

120. Ibid., line 30: ‘οὕτω σοφίας εὔρεν Σαλομὼν πλάτος’. The word πλάτος here echoes the Septuagint’s description of the ‘prudence... and abundant wisdom and breadth of heart’ that God gave to Solomon (3 Kingdoms 2.35a), cited by LSJ, s.v. πλάτος.

121. Leo Bible, dedicatory epigram (as in n. 117), lines 35–36: ‘τῶν σοφῶν θεηγόρω(ν) / εὐαγγελιστῶν’.

122. Ibid., line 38.

123. This line is discussed above, p. 16.

124. Leo Bible, dedicatory epigram (as in n. 117), line 58 (πλουτήν, read πλουτεῖν); M, alchemical epigram, line 24 (cf. line 8).

125. Leo Bible, dedicatory epigram (as in n. 117), line 42; M, alchemical epigram, line 25.

126. Leo Bible, dedicatory epigram (as in n. 117), line 5; tr. Mango, p. 62 along with n. 3. For this meaning of ἐκβάσεις in the alchemical epigram see above, n. 97.

127. Leo Bible, dedicatory epigram (as in n. 117), line 11: ‘ὡς δημιουργός’.

128. Ibid., line 2; Mango, p. 62, translates it as ‘astonishing’.

129. The results of a search in the TLG (accessed 6 Apr. 2020) for ξένως (the adverbial rather than adjectival form, because the latter lemma search produces thousands of results) include patristic examples describing miraculous or wonderful events (along with other meanings) and, especially beginning in the 9th century, dodecasyllables with ξένως at the end. For instance, Theodore the Studite plays on the meaning of ξένος, urging his audience to feed or nourish strangers (‘ξένους’, line ending), in order to be nourished wonderfully (‘ξένως’, line ending) in turn: see his *Jamben auf verschiedene Gegenstände*, ed. and tr. P. Speck, Berlin 1968, p. 270 (no. 105a). Likewise, a ‘types’ search in the DBBE (accessed 7 Apr. 2020), which yields only one result per epigram, for ξένως yielded 17 resulting lines (two from the same book epigram), including the alchemical epigram; 13 of these (or 76%) place ξένως at the end of the line.

130. Psellus, *Poemata*, ed. L. G. Westerink, Stuttgart and Leipzig 1992, p. 400 (spuria, no. 56, in 15-syllable verse), line 36, describing the transformation of the Eucharist: ‘ξένως μεταπεποιήται εἰς σῶμα τοῦ κυρίου’;

A tenth-century manuscript of the Gospels and Pauline letters in St Petersburg, National Library of Russia MS gr. 55, carries an epigram on the first verso of the opening quire.¹³¹ Like the alchemical epigram, this epigram advertises its patron's participation in the prevailing florilegic culture,¹³² calling the book it introduces a 'collection' ('συλλογήν'),¹³³ just as the alchemical epigram does (line 26); recounting that the book's patron, Basil,¹³⁴ 'collects' ('συλλέγει') divine things,¹³⁵ and concluding with the hope that posterity will see Basil as a 'broker of salvation' by means of this 'God-woven collection'.¹³⁶ Both epigrams use the stock phrase 'hidden within': bliss is 'hidden as it were' within Theodore's alchemical corpus ('ὡσπερ ἐγκεκρυμμένον', line 1); Basil bears his fervour for God 'hidden within' ('ἔνδον ... ἐγκεκρυμμένον').¹³⁷

Florence, Biblioteca Medicea Laurenziana [hereafter: Laurenziana] MS gr. 74.7 is a tenth-century collection of surgical texts dating from antiquity to the Byzantine period, taken from Hippocrates, Galen, Rufus, Paul of Aegina and others. Three epigrams praise the patron, a physician named Nicetas.¹³⁸ They are especially

this line occurs within the poem's account of how the Eucharist is sanctified during the liturgy, introduced with the words 'Τὸ δὲ πῶς ἀγιάζεται τοῦτο τὸ σῶμα μάθε' (line 26). For the spuriousness of the attribution to Psellus see A. Jacob, 'Un opusculé didactique otrantais sur la liturgie eucharistique, l'adaptation en vers, faussement attribuée à Psellos, de la «Protheoria» de Nicolas d'Andida', *Rivista di studi bizantini e neoellenici*, n.s., xiv-xvi, 1977-79, pp. 161-78. See further P. Moore, *Iter Psellianum: A Detailed Listing of Manuscript Sources for All Works Attributed to Michael Psellos*, Toronto 2005, pp. 507-08 (no. 1108).

131. Diktyon 57125. For this opening epigram in NLR MS gr. 55 see H. Belting and G. Cavallo, *Die Bibel des Niketas*, Wiesbaden 1979, p. 25; R. S. Stefec, 'Anmerkungen zu einigen handschriftlich überlieferten Epigrammen in epigraphischer Auszeichnungsmajuskel', *Jahrbuch der österreichischen Byzantinistik*, LIX, 2009, pp. 203-12 (209, with translation and several suggested improvements, which I follow); also available in the DBBE, occurrence 22996. The manuscript may have been commissioned by the powerful courtier Basil Lecapenus while he was out of favour during the reign of Emperor Romanus II (r. 959-63) or after he was exiled in 986; see Belting and Cavallo, pp. 25-26. As they explain, fol. 1 was added to the beginning of the first quire but is original to the manuscript because its headings were written in the same hand as the rest of the manuscript's headings; fol. 1^r is blank. They observe that the manuscript was produced by the same scriptorium that produced Athos, Dionysiou MS gr. 70 (diktyon 20038) in 955 for Basil Lecapenus, and on this basis argue that the Basil mentioned in the epigram is probably also Basil Lecapenus. They explain the absence of titulature in the St Petersburg manuscript by placing it during a period when Basil had fallen from grace and lost all his titles, that is, under Emperor Romanus II. For the suggestion that it could also date to 986 or later see L. Bevilacqua, 'Basilio

parakoimomenos e i manoscritti miniati: Impronte di colore nell'Ambrosiano B 119 sup., in *Vie per Bisanzio* ..., ed. A. Rigo, A. Babuin and M. Trizio, II, Bari 2013, pp. 1013-30 (1017-18). Further internal support for the hypothesis that Basil Lecapenus was the patron is offered by Stefec, pp. 210-11.

132. See P. Odorico, 'La cultura della συλλογή: 1) Il cosiddetto enciclopedismo bizantino, 2) Le tavole del sapere di Giovanni Damasceno', *Byzantinische Zeitschrift*, LXXXIII, 1990, pp. 1-21; P. Magdalino, 'Orthodoxy and History in Tenth-Century Byzantine "Encyclopedism"', in *Encyclopedic Trends in Byzantium?*, ed. P. van Deun and C. Macé, Leuven 2011, pp. 143-59 (143), who translates Odorico's 'cultura della συλλογή' as 'florilegic habit'; Roberts (as in n. 4), pp. 85-86, esp. nn. 113-14, where I propose 'florilegic culture' instead. For further discussion of florilegic culture in Byzantine book epigrams see K. Demoen, 'La poésie de la συλλογή: Les paratextes métriques des manuscrits byzantins et le (vocabulaire du) recueil', in *Pour l'amour de Byzance: Hommage à Paolo Odorico*, ed. C. Gastgeber et al., Frankfurt am Main 2013, pp. 89-98.

133. NLR MS gr. 55, opening epigram (as in n. 131), line 2.

134. See n. 131.

135. NLR MS gr. 55, opening epigram (as in n. 131), line 18.

136. NLR MS gr. 55, opening epigram (as in n. 131), lines 18-20: '[κ]αὶ τοῖς μετ' αὐτὸν πρόξενος σωτηρίας / [ὄφ]θήσεται πῶς συλλογῆ θεοπλόκῳ'. The last word alludes to the old florilegic trope (best known from anthologies of literary epigrams) of a garland woven from the 'flowers' collected by the compiler; see Lauxtermann (as in n. 33), I, p. 207 and n. 26.

137. NLR MS gr. 55, opening epigram (as in n. 131), line 13.

138. Laurenziana MS gr. 74.7 (diktyon 16662), fols 7^v-8^v (or, 8^v-9^v in the foliation stamped on the bottom

comparable to the alchemical epigram in being for the patron of a collection of texts on a *technē* or craft, in this case medicine rather than the ‘sacred art’ (‘ἡ ἱερὰ τέχνη’) and there are several examples of shared language of intellectual achievements. The alchemical epigram credits Theodore’s ‘mind renowned by all’ and his ‘famous wits’ (‘ὁ νοῦς ὁ παγγέραστος, αἱ κλειναὶ φρένες’, line 23). In the second medical epigram, the ‘wise’ patron Nicetas is praised for his ‘wits’ (‘φρένας’), which along with his hands are responsible for the ‘collection’ (‘συλλογῆς’).¹³⁹ Nicetas’s ‘mind’ (‘νοῦς’), we are told, guided the hand of the painter who illuminated the manuscript.¹⁴⁰

Also of interest is a broader similarity between the first of the three medical epigrams in Laurenziana MS gr. 74.7 and the alchemical epigram. Both devote considerable space to an advertisement of the book’s contents that takes the form ‘if you wish to learn about this *technē*, then study this book in order to find ...’. The medical epigrammatist writes: ‘If someone wishes to set legs, / femoral fractures and dislocated vertebrae, ...’ (continuing the protasis for another five lines), ‘... / then ... let him look at the images in this writing (γραφή) / and find a treatment for each injury’.¹⁴¹ This is much like the alchemical epigram’s invitation to the reader: ‘But should you wish [the book’s] gold-rich veins / to probe ... / then ... / ... / ... scrutinise the wisest writing (γραφὴν) / and you will find a wealth of higher knowledge’.¹⁴² These epigrams were clearly written by poets and for readers with a similar set of expectations for how the content and value of a book should be advertised, and even how such advertisements should be worded and structured.

I conclude this section with a prefatory book epigram for the Prophet Isaiah in a fine tenth-century manuscript, Laurenziana MS gr. 5.9, commissioned by an individual named Nicetas.¹⁴³ Here again we find an interest in the ‘mind’ (‘νοῦς’)

of rectos). All three of these epigrams were printed in Apollonius of Citium, *Illustrierter Kommentar zu der hippokratischen Schrift Περὶ ἄρθρων*, ed. H. Schöne, Leipzig 1896, pp. XII–XIV; they are re-edited in the DBBE as occurrences (first) 19488, (second) 19489 and (third) 19490. For discussion, especially of the first epigram, see Lauxtermann (as in n. 33), I, pp. 206–08.

139. Laurenziana MS gr. 74.7, second epigram (as in n. 138), lines 5–6: ‘σκόπει δὲ χεῖρας ἀφθόνως τε καὶ φρένας / σοφοῦ Νικῆτα δεξιουμένας ὄλους’. For Nicetas’s hands see also the following note. The collection is then praised for its brevity and utility: ‘ἐν οἷς ἐφαπλοῖ συλλογῆς τῷ συντόμῳ / τὴν ὠφέλειαν τοῖς λαβεῖν αἰρουμένοις’ (lines 7–8). Utility, brevity and access are common florilegic themes; see Demoen (as in n. 132); P. Odorico, ‘Du premier humanisme à l’encyclopédisme: Une construction à revoir’, *Travaux et Mémoires*, xxi.2, 2017, pp. 23–43, esp. 35–37.

140. Laurenziana MS gr. 74.7, second epigram (as in n. 138), lines 12–14: ‘καὶ νοῦς μὲν αὐτοῦ δακτύλοις τοῦ ζωγράφου / μορφᾶς ἀνιστόρησεν’. See Lampe (as in n. 77), s.v. ἀνιστορέω 2; Trapp (as in n. 83), s.v. ἀνιστορίζω. Grammatically, αὐτοῦ could in theory refer

to Christ (who appears in the previous line), but the context makes clear that this, too, describes Nicetas’s patronage of the manuscript’s production. In the following lines (15–16), the epigram continues by claiming that Nicetas’s own hands, moreover, wrote out descriptions (‘τὰς ἐκφράσεις’) of these illustrations.

142. Laurenziana MS gr. 74.7, first epigram (as in n. 138), lines 15–23: ‘οὐκοῦν ἂν τις εὐθετεῖν σκελῶν βάσιν / θραύσεις τε μηρῶν, ἐμβολὴν τῶν σπονδύλων, / ... / ... / ... / ... / ... θέλοι, / ὅδε σκοπεῖτω τῆς γραφῆς τὰς εἰκόνας / καὶ πᾶσαν εὐρήσειε τῶν παθῶν λύσιν’; tr. (modified) Lauxtermann (as in n. 33), I, p. 208.

142. Alchemical epigram, lines 3–8.

143. For the prefatory epigram in Laurenziana MS gr. 5.9 (diktyon 15957), see Belting and Cavallo (as in n. 131), p. 27 (edition and translation); Stefec (as in n. 131), p. 205 (critical edition). This manuscript is one of the three that Belting and Cavallo argued should be identified as the remains of a single multi-volume illuminated Bible, itself based on a 6th-century model, which they dubbed ‘the Niketas Bible’. For a convincing reconsideration of that argument see J. Lowden, ‘An Alternative Interpretation of the Manuscripts of Niketas’, *Byzantion*, LIII, 1983, pp.

of the person responsible for a book, in this case its author rather than its patron: the epigram says that Isaiah was ‘purified in mind by the coal of a strange flame’ and so could see the future.¹⁴⁴ Notable too is the use of the apparently commonplace word ‘strange’ (‘ξένης’), in the sense of something marvellous or wonderful, here applied not to alchemical demiurgy, the Incarnation or a book but to the fire that purified Isaiah’s mind, preparing it for prophecy.

The way this epigram describes the work of its patron is typical for dedicatory book epigrams in general (and the alchemical epigram, in particular): Nicetas, an imperial courtier and *koitonites* (one of those who served in the imperial bed-chamber), ‘put together here’ Isaiah’s words, that is, commissioned the book’s production.¹⁴⁵

None of this should be taken as an indication that the alchemical epigram was drawing on these other book epigrams as sources. Instead, what the foregoing demonstrates is that all these epigrams, including the alchemical one, were composed for readers with similar literary sensibilities. Even phrases in the alchemical epigram which might, at first sight, be read as indicating an esoteric or occultist mindset (the golden contents ‘hidden’ within the book; the ‘strange’ manipulations of matter that it describes; and so on) turn out on closer inspection to be part of the standard vocabulary that middle Byzantine epigrammatists used to advertise books, especially technical books, to potential readers.

6. Conclusions

This article has shown that the alchemical epigram was almost certainly composed for M: its metre strongly suggests a middle Byzantine, not late antique date, and its occasional scribal errors are consistent with copying from a poet’s draft. Meanwhile, palaeography has helped situate this well known and much studied manuscript more securely in the tenth century. A comparison to literature current in that century, and especially to other dedicatory book epigrams, has made clear that the alchemical epigram was entirely standard for its day. This evidence suggests that little distinguished the Byzantine reader of alchemical texts from learned Byzantine readers of technical literature more generally.

M is a strange and remarkable collection (‘συλλογὴν ξένην’), as the poet emphasises. But this strangeness does not place M, or its reader, on the margins of Byzantine culture. On the contrary, Byzantine readers were delighted to be confronted with strange ideas. Much knowledge was fraught in middle Byzantine culture. Hellenic literature offered an array of sciences and crafts that were for many reasons desirable, from rhetoric to theology, from physics to astrology. What was problematic about them was not only that they represented a pagan past, but also that the ideas themselves could challenge conventional beliefs. This was hardly

559–74, who also argued (pp. 567–68) that it is misleading to refer to ‘the Niketas Bible’ since the volumes probably never comprised a complete Bible.

144. Laurenziana MS gr. 5.9, prefatory epigram (as in n. 143), lines 2–3: ‘τὸν νοῦν καθαρθεὶς ἀνθρακι

φλογὸς ξένης / καὶ δὴ τὸ μέλλον ὡς ἐνεστῶς προβλέπων’.

145. Ibid., lines 10–11: ‘ὄν στέφους κοιτῶν ἔχει / ... συντέθεικεν ἐνθάδε’.

new in the eleventh century; after all, Socrates was already controversial among his ancient Athenian contemporaries—and that was surely part of his appeal. The alchemical epigram, in its endeavour to promote ‘this book of all-wise thoughts’ (line 27), was making an appeal to readers of the standard ‘classics’ of the high-brow Byzantine reading list, the *logoi*,¹⁴⁶ asking them to view alchemy as a distinguished *technē*, like medicine, and to see alchemical texts as part and parcel of their ancient literary heritage, stretching from Plato to the Evangelists to Gregory of Nazianzus—all to be read in a comfortable reclining pose *sub tegmine Christi*.¹⁴⁷

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Index of Manuscripts

ATHOS

DIONYSIOU

gr. 70 (diktyon 20038): p. 52 n. 131

BERLIN

STAATSBIBLIOTHEK (BSB)

gr. 134 (Phillipps 1538, diktyon 9439): p. 74, p. 76
 nm. 52–53 and 55, p. 76, p. 83 n. 66, pp. 87–88;
 illustrations p. 74 Fig. 4, p. 87 Fig. 9, p. 88 Fig. 11
 gr. fol. 73 (diktyon 9163): p. 76, p. 84 n. 69, p. 83;
 illustration p. 77 Fig. 6

FLORENCE

BIBLIOTECA MEDICEA LAURENZIANA (Laurenziana)

gr. 5.9 (diktyon 15957): pp. 87–88
 gr. 74.7 (diktyon 16662): pp. 87–88

PARIS

BIBLIOTHÈQUE NATIONALE DE FRANCE (BnF)

gr. 12 (diktyon 49572): p. 80 n. 106
 gr. 1640 (diktyon 51263): p. 83 n. 74
 gr. 2322 (diktyon 51953): p. 84 n. 67

PATMOS

MONASTERY OF ST JOHN THE THEOLOGIAN

gr. 163 (diktyon 54407): p. 84 n. 60

ST PETERSBURG

NATIONAL LIBRARY OF RUSSIA

gr. 55 (diktyon 57125): p. 85

VATICAN CITY

BIBLIOTECA APOSTOLICA VATICANA (BAV)

Barb. gr. 310 (diktyon 64853): pp. 87–88;
 illustrations p. 85 Fig. 5, p. 87 Fig. 8
 gr. 1650 (diktyon 68281): p. 8 n. 25
 Reg. gr. 1 (Leo Bible) (diktyon 66171): pp. 87–88

VENICE

BIBLIOTECA NAZIONALE MARCIANA

gr. 134 (diktyon 69605): p. 80 n. 106
 gr. 299 (M) (diktyon 69770): pp. 1–84;
 illustrations p. 7 Fig. 1, pp. 82–83 Figs 2–3, p. 84
 Fig. 7, p. 82 Fig. 10
 gr. 524 (diktyon 69995): p. 8 n. 14

146. Papaioannou (as in n. 71), p. 18.

147. *Anthologia latina*, no. 765, line 1; cf. Virgil, *Eclogues*, 1.1.